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SoildiverAgro

Soil biodiversity enhancement in European agroecosystems to promote their stability and resilience by external inputs reduction and crop performance increase

D6.2 - REPORT ON ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS OF SOIL DIVERSITY ENHANCING MANAGEMENT PRACTICES

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Summary

A comparative analysis of crop management practices was conducted using the Life Cycle Assessment methodology with the objective of evaluating their environmental performance and identifying the most sustainable options. Six case studies were selected, spanning five climatic zones over a period of three years. Each year, different management practices were tested, including crop rotation, organic farming, tillage methods, and nutrient application. Two functional units were used for comparison: an economic unit (€1 of gross margin) and a land-based unit (1 ha of cultivated land). This assessment helped identify the main contributing factors to environmental impacts and revealed links between soil biodiversity and associated ecosystem services.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
CFs	Characterization Factors
CS	Case study
CTU	Comparative toxic unit
CTUe	Comparative toxic unit for ecosystem toxicity Impacts
EC₅₀	Median Effective Concentration
EF	Environmental Footprint
EfF	Effect Factor
eq	Equivalent
EU	European Union
FEC	Freshwater ecotoxicity
FET	Freshwater eutrophication
FR	Fossil resource scarcity
FU	Functional Unit
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
GW	Global Warming
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LU	Land Use
MEC	Marine ecotoxicity
MET	Marine eutrophication
MJ	Mega Joules
MR	Minerals resource scarcity
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
PEFCR	Product Environmental Footprint Category Rule
POF	Photochemical ozone formation
PPP	Plant protection products
SOD	Stratospheric ozone depletion
T	Treatment
TA	Terrestrial acidification
TBD	To Be Determined
TEC	Terrestrial ecotoxicity
WFLDB	World food LCA database
WU	Water Use
Y	Year

1. Introduction

SoildiverAgro is driven by a long-term vision of promoting harmonious relationships between crop production, biodiversity, and the provision of ecosystem services at local, regional, and global scales. Its primary goal is to encourage the adoption of novel management practices and cropping systems that enrich soil genetic and functional biodiversity. These practices aim to reduce reliance on external inputs while simultaneously boosting crop production and quality, enhancing the delivery of ecosystem services, and fortifying the stability and resilience of European Union (EU) agriculture.

The project focuses on the implementation of innovative management practices grounded in soil mycorrhiza and plant growth-promoting bacteria, including the development and testing of new commercial products. It also encompasses the prudent management of soil organisms, such as fungivores, the utilization of appropriate crop rotations, multiple cropping and intercropping, the integration of nutrient catch crops, the deployment of trap crops for pest control, the utilization of by-products to improve soil health, and the application of suitable tillage systems.

Among the various outcomes of SoildiverAgro, the project aims to improve the sustainability performance of the proposed crop management practices within the project, with special attention to the reduction of soil contamination, mitigation of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and amplification of soil carbon sequestration. To do so, an environmental analysis has been conducted, presented in this document, which will allow to establish strategies for more environmentally sustainable agricultural practices, as well as to inform updates to existing EU policies.

There are several analytical tools to properly assess environmental sustainability, among which the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) stands out for its holistic perspective, which considers the entire life cycle of a product, process or service, and its broad scope of environmental indicators (e.g., climate change, water depletion, eutrophication, ecotoxicity, among others). Therefore, the LCA methodology has been selected as the framework for conducting the environmental analysis of the different crop management practices.

This document corresponds to Deliverable 6.2: Report on Environmental Impacts of Soil Diversity-Enhancing Management Practices, aligning with Sub-task 6.2.1 of the SoildiverAgro project. The report aims to conduct an environmental analysis and comparison of six case studies on crop management practices within the SoildiverAgro project using life cycle assessment methodology. Its purpose is to provide stakeholders with insights into the environmental performance of these practices, supporting informed decision-making.

The report begins with the definition of materials and methods used in the study (Section 2), including the goal, scope, system boundaries, and functional units (Section 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3). This is followed by the life cycle inventory analysis in Section 2.4, the life cycle impact assessment in Section 2.5, and a description of the case studies in Section 2.6. Section 3 presents the interpretation of results, highlighting the main factors contributing to environmental impacts. The document concludes with a summary of findings in Section 4.

2. Materials and methods

The Life Cycle Assessment was the methodology chosen to evaluate the environmental impacts of the proposed crop management practices within SoildiverAgro project. To do so, the four steps outlined in the ISO standard 14040 (ISO, 2006) were followed (**Figure 1**):

1. Goal and scope definition. This phase involves clearly outlining the intended application and the scope of the study.
2. Life cycle inventory (LCI). During this step, information about the product system is gathered, and the relevant inputs and outputs are quantified.
3. Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA). Here, the flows identified in the inventory phase are translated into indicators that measure potential environmental impacts.
4. Interpretation. In the final phase, the outcomes from the previous stages are combined and evaluated to meet the predefined study goals.

Figure 1: Stages of an LCA according to EN (ISO 14040, 2006).

2.1. Goal and scope definition

The main objective of this environmental analysis is to evaluate the environmental performance of the crop management practices (hereafter referred to as "treatments") proposed within the project and to compare their performance in order to identify those most environmentally sustainable, while increasing or maintaining their production yield.

This environmental analysis is structured in a set of case studies settled in five different climate zones and run over a three-years period. In each case study, different treatments were tested

every year, including crop rotation, organic farming, various tillage methods, and the application of nutrients.

2.1.1. Intended audience

The findings of this LCA study are intended for the partners within the consortium, with a particular emphasis on the SoildiverAgro crop growers, as well as growers outside the project and policy makers. The objective of this study is to provide stakeholders with insights into the environmental performance of crop management practices, thereby facilitating more informed decision-making.

2.2. System boundaries

A "cradle-to-farm gate" scope has been adopted, meaning that all impacts from the extraction of raw materials to the harvest of agricultural products were considered (**Figure 2**). In particular, the activities included within the system boundaries include planting, ridging, crop protection measures, fertilization and harvesting, as well as the production processes of all inputs (e.g., energy, seeds, agrochemicals), and the machinery used.

Figure 2: System boundaries of SoildiverAgro project.

2.3. Functional unit

The choice of functional unit (FU) is crucial because it defines the basis for comparing the environmental impacts of different agricultural systems, and depending on the choice, results can differ importantly. Traditionally, land-based (e.g., 1 ha of cultivated land) and productive (e.g., 1 kg of primary crop harvest) FUs have been used. However, these FUs can be limiting, especially when considering the multifunctionality of agricultural systems. In many cases, different functions (e.g., ecosystem services) and secondary products are overlooked or not properly accounted. To address this limitation, Kopton et al. (2023) suggested using a monetary functional unit as a more appropriate approach, such as the operation profit.

Following their recommendation, **1 euro of profit** has been selected as the FU, thereby enabling the accounting for the value of all products generated by the agricultural system, as opposed to solely the primary product. This FU incorporates an economic perspective of agricultural systems, a key driver in decision-making, by offering insights into the impact per euro of profit. It is important to note, however, that monetary FUs are subject to fluctuations in market prices over time, which can significantly influence the results of environmental analysis. It is therefore recommended analyzing agricultural systems using more than one FU (González-García et al., 2021), in order to consider different perspectives and obtain a more comprehensive assessment. In this regard, an additional FU, **1 ha of cultivated land**, has been selected. This land-based FU provides information about the type of management that minimizes environmental impacts regardless of productivity or revenue.

2.4. Life cycle inventory

The LCI process involves the classification and quantification of the input and output flows at every stage of the product or system's life cycle. Two types of data are typically reported within an LCI: primary data and secondary data.

The foreground system consists of primary data that is directly related to the activities under control. Primary data were collected directly from the field (by farmers and researchers) and included details related to the agricultural practices and the production of agricultural products (**Annex A: Life cycle inventory**). The collected primary data included the following:

- Yield: the quantity of agricultural products harvested in kg.
- Precipitation: data on the amount of rainfall received, which can significantly impact crop growth and fertilizer leaching into water bodies.
- Total Area of Experiments: information regarding the size and location of the experimental plots.
- Agrochemicals: data on the use of various inputs, including mineral and organic fertilizers, herbicides, fungicides, and insecticides.
- Irrigation water: the amount of water applied for irrigation.

- Electricity: information on the use of electricity in farming operations.
- Diesel: data related to the diesel consumption of the machinery.
- Seeds: data about the type and quantity of seeds used.
- Nutrients applied: details on the specific nutrients applied to the soil.
- Tillage: information regarding the type of tillage practices used.
- Soil data: collection of soil samples for analysis before and during the experiment, including bulk density, clay and silk content, pH, as well as the presence of minerals or heavy metals in the soil.

The background system relates to those parts of the system that are not under control and thus, from which no primary data can be gathered. In this study, it included the raw material extraction and manufacturing processes for agrochemicals. Secondary data was sourced from the Ecoinvent database 3.9.1 (using the system model “allocation, cut off”) (Wernet et al., 2016), AGRIBALYSE® 3.1 (Colomb et al., 2015) and the World Food LCA Database (WFLDB) (Nemecek et al., 2019). Since SoildiverAgro is being conducted among six European countries to ensure that the results and insights gained are applicable and relevant across different European regions and territories, the secondary data gathered were average European data.

Furthermore, emissions occurring in the field due to the application of agrochemicals, as well due to changes in land use, were estimated using empirical models in line with the WFLDB modelling guidelines. **Table 1** outlines the emission models that were used.

Table 1: Overview of the emission models recommended by the World Food LCA Database 3.5 (WFLDB).

Emission	WFLDB 3.5	Source
Ammonia (NH ₃)	EMEP Tier 2	EEA (2016) IPCC (2006)
Nitrous oxide (N ₂ O)	IPCC (2006) Tier 1	IPCC (2006)
Nitrate (NO ₃ ⁻)	The SQCB-NO ₃ model	Faist Emmenegger et al. (2009)
Phosphorus (P, PO ₄ ³⁻)	SALCA-P	Prasuhn (2006)

The emissions associated with mineral fertilizers were modeled according to the following methodology:

Ammonia (NH₃): for NH₃ emissions, the European Environment Agency (EEA) and the European Monitoring and Assessment Program (EMEP/EEA, 2019) were used. NH₃ emissions are calculated based on several factors, including soil pH, climate conditions, and the type of fertilizer used. The conversion factor for counting NH₃ emissions from N fertilizer application is 17/14.

Nitrous oxide (NO_x): NO_x emissions primarily result from the nitrification process. An emission factor of 0.012 kg NO_x-N per kg of N was applied. This factor is used to both mineral and organic fertilizers, including animal manure (EMEP/EEA, 2019). It is important to note that NO_x emissions from the application of N fertilizers are relatively small compared to other sources (Nemecek et al., 2019).

N₂O emissions: occur during nitrification and denitrification processes. The estimation of N₂O emissions follows the IPCC guidelines (IPCC, 2006a) Volume 4 Tier 1 for crop production. N₂O emissions are influenced by various factors, including N fertilizer application (both mineral and organic), N content in crop residues, N from the mineralization of soil organic matter, losses of N in the form of ammonia, nitrogen oxides, and nitrate. N₂O emissions were computed by using an emission factor of 44/28.

Nitrate (NO₃⁻): the model developed by Faist Emmenegger et al. (2009) was used to estimate the leaching of NO₃⁻ to groundwater. For modeling them, farmers were required to provide information related to precipitation and irrigation, fertilizer type, root depth and N uptake for each crop. Moreover, clay content, carbon content and bulk density data were obtained from analyzes of soil samples carried out by the Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena (UPCT) for each case study.

Phosphorus (P, PO₄³⁻): phosphorus has low mobility in the soil due to its limited solubility. Therefore, due to the high P demand of crops, excess P is often applied. As a result, this excess of P often leads to contamination of both surface and groundwater, as it dissolves easily in these water sources. According to Pietrzak et al. (2020), despite the high probability of P loss from soils through surface runoff, there is a concurrent shortage of available P for plant uptake. These results highlight a discrepancy in the assessment of soil P concentration that creates a contradiction. This uncertainty is exacerbated by the lack of correlation between the P saturation index and other critical factors influencing P runoff losses, such as crop type and land slope. In this line, WFLDB proposes SALCA-P model (Prasuhn, 2006), which focuses solely on the analysis of P emissions to groundwater and surface water, minimizing inconsistencies and uncertainties in the calculations. Three pathways for phosphorus emissions to water are calculated by the SALCA-P model (Prasuhn, 2006):

- **Leaching of soluble phosphate (PO₄) to groundwater:** the conversion factor used to estimate this type of phosphorus emission is 0.07 kg P/ha*yr per kg P/ha.
- **Run-off of soluble phosphate to surface water:** to quantify the run-off of soluble phosphate into surface water, a conversion factor of 0.175 kg P/ha*yr per kg P/ha supplied with fertilization is used.
- **Erosion of soil particles containing phosphorus:** these emissions were calculated using several factors, including the phosphorus content in the topsoil layer, as erosivity, erodibility, slope and practice (p) factors. An average value of 0.00095 kg P/kg soil was used for the phosphorus content in the topsoil layer. The crop factor (c1) was obtained from literature (**Table 2**) and the tillage (c2) factor was selected depending on the type of tillage: 1 for conventional tillage, 0.35 for conservation/furrow tillage and 0.25 for no-till practices. The remaining factors (erosivity, erodibility, slope and p-factor) were obtained from Panagos et al. (2022).

Table 2: Crop and their crop factor as assumed for calculations

Crop	Crop factor	Source
Potato	0.34	Panagos et al. (2015)
Broccoli	0.56	Mtalo et al. (2019)

Barley	0.3	Panagos et al. (2015)
Melon	0.45	Allen et al. (1998)
Leek	0.35	Allen et al. (1998)
Celery	0.7	Allen et al. (1998)
Cauliflower	0.7	Allen et al. (1998)
Wheat	0.20	Panagos et al. (2015)
Maize	0.38	Panagos et al. (2015)
Peas	0.5	Allen et al. (1998)

Moreover, methane emissions due to *manure application* were estimated using a conversion of organic manure to methane reported by IPCC (2006, Table 10.17). The temperature of the region where the manure is applied was considered in the selection of the IPCC values (**Table 3**).

Table 3: Methane conversion factors for each manure management system for the cool climate, temperate and warm climates. Source: ((IPCC, 2006), Table 10.17).

Categories IPCC (2006)	MCF Cool (<15°C)	MCF Temperate (15-25°C)	MCF Warm (>25°C)
Pasture	1.0%	1.5%	2.0%
Liquid / slurry	20.0%	42.0%	75.0%
Anaerobic digester	2.0%	2.0%	2.0%
Cattle and swine	20.0%	42.0%	78.0%
Composting (static pile)	0.5%	0.5%	0.5%
Poultry manure	1.5%	1.5%	1.5%

With respect to the modeling of *metals and micronutrient emissions*, the methodological procedures remain under development (Nemecek et al., 2019). Accordingly, the soil sampling data provided by UPCT, were used to account for these emissions. The heavy metals and nutrients analyzed by UPCT include calcium, sodium, magnesium, iron, manganese, copper, zinc, boron, and molybdenum.

Regarding emissions from *plant protection products (PPP)*, WFLDB recommendations were followed, assuming that 100 % of the active ingredients of PPPs end up in the in the soil. **Table 4** summarizes the PPPs used by each case study (except for CS14b, which does not use PPPs) listing the crop, name, type, and PPP active ingredients. The quantities applied to each treatment are detailed in **Annex A: Life cycle inventory**.

Table 4: Overview of plant protection products and associated active ingredients per case study and crop.

Case study	Crop	Name of the product	Type	Active ingredient
1	Potato	Ralbi-10	Insecticide	Cypermethrin 10%
		Carial-Top	Fungicide	Mandipropamid 25% and difenoconazole 25%

	Broccoli	Eclipse 70 WG	Herbicide	Metribuzin 70%
		Lycos	Herbicide	Metazachlor 50%
		Karate zeon	Insecticide	Lambda cyhalothrin 10%
	Melon	Ortiva	Fungicide	Azoxystrobin 22.8%
		Maxofen EC	Herbicide	Oxyfluorphen 24%
		Azufega	Fungicide	Sulfur 98.5%
		Cal-Ex	Insecticide	Abamectin 1.8%
		Actum	Fungicide	Boscalide 20% and kresoxim-methyl 10%
4	Potato	Metric	Herbicide	Metribuzin 40%
		Volare	Fungicide	Fluopicolide 6.25% and propamocarb 52.5%
		Epik	Insecticide	Acetamiprid 20%
		Kabuto	Fungicide	Difenoconazole 1.67%
		Sumifive	Insecticide	Esfenvalerate 50%
		Milraz pro	Fungicide	Cymoxanil 33% and zoxamide 33%.
		Gonzai	Herbicide	Piraflufen ethyl 2.65%
		Bismark	Herbicide	Pendimethalin and clomazone 5.5%
		Xanilo	Fungicide	Cymoxanil 45%
		Revus	Fungicide	Mandipropamid 23.4%
		Lieto	Fungicide	Cymoxanil 33% and Zoxamide 33%
				Leimay
8	Leek	Rapsan 500	Herbicide	Metazachlor 50%
		Stomp Aqua	Herbicide	Pendimethalin 45.5%
		Xinca	Herbicide	Bromoxynil 40%
		Lentagran 45 WP	Herbicide	Pyridate 45%
		Benevia	Insecticide	Cyantraniliprole 10%
		Conserve pro	Insecticide	Spinosad 12%
		Vertimec	Insecticide	Abamectin 1.84%
		Tebusip	Fungicide	Tebuconazole 25%
	Celery	Stomp aqua	Herbicide	Pendimethalin 45.5%
		Metarex Inov	Molluscicide	Metaldehyde 4%
		Centium	Herbicide	Clomazone 36%
		Defi	Herbicide	Prosulfocarbe 80%
		Challenge	Herbicide	Aclonifen 60%
		Ortiva Top	Fungicide	Azoxystrobin 20% and difenoconazole 12.5%
		Conserve pro	Insecticide	Spinosad 12%
		Nativo 75	Fungicide	Tebuconazole 50% and trifloxystrobin 25%
		Ultor	Insecticide	Spirotetramat 14.5%
11	Wheat	Durano	Herbicide	Glyphosate 36%

		Boxer	Herbicide	Florasulam 4.84%
		Herold	Herbicide	Diflufenican 20% and flufenacet 40%
		Input Classic	Fungicide	Prothioconazole 16% and spiroxamine 30%
		Prodax	Fungicide	Prohexadione-calcium 5% and trinexapac-ethyl 7.5%
		Comet	Fungicide	Pyraclostrobin 20%
		Revytrex	Fungicide	Mefentrifluconazole 11.6%, pyraclostrobin 15.5% and fluxapyroxad 7.74%
		Fezan	Fungicide	Tebuconazole 25%
		Aznany	Fungicide	Fluroxypyr-methylheptyl 28.8%
		Karate Zeon	Insecticide	Lambda cyhalothrin 9.43%
		Pointer plus	Herbicide	Metsulfuron-methyl 8.3%, florasulam 10.5% and tribenuron 8.3%
	Maize	Aspect	Herbicide	2,4-D choline salt 43.6% and picloram triisopropano-lamine salt 14.4%
		Maister	Herbicide	Foramsulfuron 30% and isoxadifen-ethyl 30%
	Wheat	Boxer	Herbicide	Florasulam 4.84%
		Mertil	Herbicide	Metsulfuron methyl 75%
		Moddus	Growth regulator	Trinexapac-ethyl 25%
		Pointer plus	Herbicide	Metsulfuron-methyl 8.3%, florasulam 10.5% and tribenuron 8.3%
		Input Classic	Fungicide	Prothioconazole 16% and spiroxamine 30%
		Axial 50	Herbicide	Pinoxaden 5%
		Balaya	Fungicide	Pyraclostrobin 9.78% and triazole-ethanol 9.78%
Caramba		Fungicide	Methconazole 9%	
Curbatur		Fungicide	Cymoxanil 60%	
Karate Zeon	Insecticide	Lambda cyhalothrin 9.43%		

The quantification of *soil carbon sequestration* was based on soil analyses conducted by the UPCT. In particular, the following parameters were used in the calculation: total organic carbon (TOC), particulate organic carbon (POC), bulk density, and the proportion of fine particles. The data were used to calculate the soil organic carbon (SOC) content in accordance with the procedure outlined by Rojo Serrano et al. 2022). Subsequently, the carbon sequestration was

quantified as the difference between the SOC content in two consecutive years. The carbon sequestration values were subsequently transformed into CO₂ equivalents using the 44/12 ratio.

2.5. Life cycle impact assessment

The ReCiPe hierarchist (H) midpoint method (v1.06) (Huijbregts et al., 2017) was used to translate the life cycle inventory into environmental impacts. Particularly, twelve midpoint impact categories were selected based on their relevance in agricultural systems (**Table 5**). The computations were performed using the SimaPro 9.5 software.

The rationale behind the decision to use ReCiPe method is related to the cost-benefit analysis (CBA) that is being conducted by Universidad de Vigo (UVigo) reported as Deliverable 6.3. The objective of this CBA is to quantify all costs and benefits associated with the crop management practices studied, including the environmental externalities calculated by the LCA in physical units. To translate these values into monetary terms, the Environmental Prices Handbook (de Bruyn et al., 2018) will be used, with the particularity that its monetary factors are aligned with indicators of the ReCiPe method. Accordingly, the ReCiPe method was deemed the most appropriate for the environmental impact assessment to align with the UVigo analysis.

Table 5: Overview of selected midpoint impact categories and related impact indicators of ReCiPe method.

Impact category	Abbreviation	Indicator	Unit
Climate change	GW	Infra-red radiative forcing increases	kg CO ₂ to air
Ozone depletion	SOD	Stratospheric ozone decreases	kg CFC-11 to air
Terrestrial acidification	TA	Proton increases in natural soils	kg SO ₂ to air
Freshwater eutrophication	FET	Phosphorus increases in fresh water	kg P to fresh water
Marine eutrophication	MET	Dissolved inorganic nitrogen increases in marine water	Kg N to marine water
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	TEC	Hazard-weighted increases in natural soils	kg 1,4- DCB to industrial soil
Freshwater ecotoxicity	FEC	Hazard-weighted increases in fresh waters	kg 1,4- DCB to fresh water
Marine ecotoxicity	MEC	Hazard-weighted increases in marine water	kg 1,4- DCB to marine water
Land use	LU	Occupation and time integrated transformation	m ² -yr annual crop land
Water use	WU	Increase of water consumed	m ³ water consumed
Mineral resource scarcity	MR	Ore grade decreases	kg Cu

Fossil resource scarcity	FR	Upper heating value	kg oil
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2.6. Description of the case studies

In the SoildiverAgro project, 15 case studies were designed and established across six different pedoclimatic regions. However, only six case studies will be included in this LCA. Several limitations, such as harvest loss, contributed to the exclusion of the other studies. The inputs applied to each case study are detailed in **Annex A: Life cycle inventory**.

The Table 6 provides a detailed description of the six selected case studies, which span five distinct pedoclimatic regions: Mediterranean, Lusitanian, Central Atlantic, Continental, and Boreal.

Table 6: Overview of SoildiverAgro case studies.

Case study	Location	Climate	Current practices	Management practices implemented	Crops
1	Cartagena, Spain	Mediterranean	Conventional farming (fertigation)	Reduce mineral fertilization, addition of nutrient solubilizing biological agents and crop rotation	Potato, broccoli, and melon
4	Xinzo de Limia, Spain	Lusitanian	Conventional agriculture and crop rotation (vegetables-cereal)	Application of mycorrhiza to potato crop and reduce mineral P fertilization	Potato
8	Sint-Katelijne-Waver, Belgium	Atlantic Central	Organic (intensive, inverting tillage, farmyard manure and organic granular fertilizer) and conventional horticulture (intensive inverting tillage, mineral fertilizer and animal slurry)	Addition of organic matter: addition of compost and animal manure instead of slurry. Non-inverting tillage and use of cover crops in autumn/spring (before or after main crop)	Leek, celery and cauliflower

9	Beveren, Belgium	Atlantic Central	Agro-ecological system, agro-forestry, locally produced organic matter, cover crops incorporated and reduced tillage	Alternative to green manure like fermented organic waste and zero mineral fertilization	Wheat
11	Nideggen, Germany	Continental	Conventional agriculture, reduced tillage (ploughless), mineral fertilizer and N fertilization	Crop rotation, no pesticides, clover undersowing, and reduced sowing rate.	Wheat, maize
14b	South Karelia, Finland	Boreal	Inversion tillage (moldboard plowing) and plant cover	Minimal or reduced tillage, crop rotation, cover crops and organic farming practices	Wheat, peas

Table 7 illustrates the crop cycle of the different case studies for the selected period.

Table 7: Crop calendar of SoildiverAgro case studies.

Case study	Year	Crops	Months														
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12			
1	2021	Potato															
	2022	Broccoli															
	2023	Melon															
4	2021	Potato															
	2022	Barley															
	2023	Potato															
8	2020	Leek															
	2021	Celery															
	2022	Cauliflower															
9	2020	Wheat															
	2021	Wheat															
	2022	Wheat															
11	2020	Wheat															
	2021	Wheat															
	2022	Maize															
14b	2020	Wheat															

	2021	Wheat and peas Wheat			
	2022				
	2023				

2.6.1. Case study 1 (Spain): Use of soil biodiversity to reduce the prevalence of soil-borne diseases and pests and increase nutrient availability in potatoes cropped in multiple cropping and rotations

In this case study, a multifaceted strategy has been employed to reduce reliance on pesticides, minimize excessive fertilizer and irrigation use, and enhance overall crop quality, soil fertility, and the microbial ecosystem. This approach involves the concurrent introduction of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) and plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR), alongside appropriate mineral fertilizer applications. This integrated approach not only promotes superior crop quality and enriches soil fertility but also fosters a more favorable microbial environment. AMF and PGPR exhibit both direct and indirect effects on plant development, including phytohormone production, heightened nutrient and water availability, and a comprehensive defense against various biotic and abiotic stressors (Ollio et al., 2022).

To enhance soil quality, crop rotation practices were also incorporated. The sequence of crops harvested on the study plots was as follows: potato (harvested in 2021), broccoli (harvested in 2022) and melon (harvested in 2023) (**Table 7**). This crop rotation strategy, as depicted visually in the figure below (**Figure 3**), helped diversify the crops grown in each year.

A total of 16 plots, each measuring 6 by 35 meters, were selected for the experiment within the "Finca Tomás Ferro" situated in Cartagena, specifically in La Palma (Spain). Four distinct treatments were implemented, as outlined below:

- **T1 – Control 100% (conventional fertilization):** this treatment represents the baseline conventional approach, where standard fertilization practices were followed.
- **T2 – Control fertilization reduction:** these two sub-treatments within the study involved reducing fertilization by 70% for potato crops, 50% for broccoli crops and 50% for melon crops, respectively, without the introduction of additional biological agents.
- **T3 – NUVE (biological agents + 70% reduction in fertilizer):** under this treatment, biological agents were introduced, along with a 70% reduction in fertilizer application compared to the conventional method.
- **T4 – BACTONECO (nutrient-solubilizing biological bacteria + 70% reduction in fertilizer):** in this treatment, nutrient-solubilizing biological bacteria were utilized in conjunction with a 70% reduced fertilizer regimen.

Figure 3: Visual representation of crop management practices and main objectives in SoildiverAgro Case study 1.

2.6.2. Case study 4 (Spain): Use of mycorrhiza in potato fields to reduce the incidence of common scab, decrease the use of phosphorus fertilizers, increase crop yields and soil biodiversity

The implementation of mycorrhizae in this study aims not only to improve potato production and its market value, but also to address the challenges posed by acidic soils and low phosphorus availability in the Lusitanian region. The symbiotic relationship of mycorrhizal fungi with plants improves the ability of potatoes to absorb phosphorus from the soil (Pérez-Rodríguez et al., 2022). By improving the plant's ability to absorb phosphorus, the use of mycorrhizae can lead to a reduction in the amount of phosphorus fertilizer required, which can be cost-effective and beneficial to the environment. Additionally, mycorrhizae can help protect crops, such as potatoes, from common scab, a damaging disease that affects tubers.

The sequence of crops harvested on the study plots was as follows: potato (harvested in 2021), barley (harvested in 2022) and potato (harvested in 2023) (**Table 7**). In the case study conducted in Xinzo da Limia (Spain), 20 plots were designated for experimentation, and five distinct treatments were applied as follows:

- **T1 – Conventional:** this treatment utilized conventional phosphorus fertilization, specifically mineral P in association with superphosphate.

- **T2 – 50% Mineral P fertilizer and no mycorrhiza:** in this treatment, only half of the mineral P fertilizer used in the conventional treatment (T1) is applied, and mycorrhiza is not employed.
- **T3 – No mineral P fertilizer and no mycorrhiza:** this treatment avoided the use of superphosphate fertilization entirely and did not incorporate mycorrhiza.
- **T4 – 50% Mineral P fertilizer and single strain mycorrhiza:** in this treatment, only half of the mineral P fertilizer used in the conventional treatment (T1) is employed, and it included the use of a single strain of mycorrhiza.
- **T5 – No mineral P fertilizer and single strain mycorrhiza:** this treatment avoided using superphosphate fertilization and solely relied on a single strain of mycorrhiza for phosphorus uptake.

2.6.3. Case study 8 (Belgium): Extensification of conventional and organic vegetable farming

This case study serves as a comprehensive comparison of various farming approaches, covering conventional farming versus organic farming, as well as intensive farming (with conventional tillage and no cover crops) versus extensive farming (with reduced tillage, cover crops and compost applications) (**Figure 4**). The organic farming approach integrates the use of organic matter as a fertilizer (Fleerackers & Van den Eynde, 2022).

In this case, the crop rotation consisted of leek (harvested in 2020), then celery (harvested in 2021) and ended with cauliflower (harvested in 2022).

Moreover, two fields were used for this trial. The first field has been conventionally cultivated for several years, following an intensive vegetable rotation, and the second one has been recently converted to organic farming. During the two-year conversion period, it was sown with a grass-clover mixture to enhance soil quality and fertility. Both fields were divided into two halves, each employing a different cultivation system. This division resulted in four distinct treatments:

- **T1 – Conventional and intensive (control):** the intensively cultivated plots in this treatment are characterized by inverting tillage and the absence of cover crops in the crop rotation. Mineral fertilizers are used for soil nutrient supplementation.
- **T2 – Conventional and extensive:** in the conventional extensive treatment, compost is used along with chemical fertilizer for soil enrichment. Reduced tillage practices are employed in this approach and cover crops are used.
- **T3 – Organic and intensive:** organic fields are fertilized using organic fertilizer like cattle slurry, farmyard manure (cattle), and NK (11-3) organic fertilizer. Inverting tillage is utilized for soil management.
- **T4 – Organic and extensive:** similar to T3, organic fertilizer is the primary source of soil nutrients in this treatment together with green waste compost. However, reduced tillage methods are implemented, and cover crops are used.

Figure 4: Visual representation of crop management practices and main objectives in SoildiverAgro Case study 8.

2.6.4. Case study 9 (Belgium): Improving agro-ecological wheat and potato production by application of different sources of green manure

In this study, the design focuses on assessing the advantages of incorporating (fermented) organic waste into wheat and potato production (**Figure 5**). These types of fertilizers have the potential to significantly impact microbial diversity and activity in the soil, leading to the production of natural antibiotics, essential vitamins, and plant growth hormones. This, in turn, is believed to enhance soil quality and resilience against pests and diseases (Bauwens & Waeyenberge, 2022).

The sequence of crops harvested on the study plots was as follows: wheat (harvested in 2020), wheat (harvested in 2021) and potato (harvested in 2022).

A field operating under an agroecological farming system and incorporating agroforestry practices were divided into four equal parts. Each part received a different source of green manure, and in one case, no additional organic material at all. The treatments are as follows:

- **T1 – Cattle manure:** this treatment involved the use of cattle manure in combination with catch crops. Catch crops are generally fast-growing crops planted to capture excess nutrients and improve soil health.

- **T2 – Worm compost:** worm compost is used in this treatment in conjunction with catch crops.
- **T3 – Grass silage:** grass silage, a type of fermented forage crop, is used along with catch crops in this treatment.
- **T4 – Control:** the control treatment did not incorporate additional organic material. However, catch crops are still applied to enhance soil health.

Figure 5: Visual representation of crop management practices and main objectives in SoildiverAgro Case study 9.

2.6.5. Case study 11 (Germany): Soil biodiversity enhancement in European agroecosystems to promote their stability and resilience by external inputs reduction and crop performance increase

This case study was designed with the objective of assessing the potential of plant diversity in conventional wheat cultivation to reduce fungal diseases, such as *Fusarium sp.*, by promoting antagonistic fungivorous soil fauna and enhancing soil self-regulatory processes (Bind et al., 2022).

In this case, the crop rotation consisted of wheat (harvested in 2021), then maize (harvested in 2022) and then wheat (harvested in 2023). The trials were carried out in Nideggen (North Rhine-Westphalia, Germany) on a total of 12 plots, each measuring 9 by 40 meters. Three distinct treatments were implemented as follows:

- **T1 – Control:** this group represents conventional farming and serves as the baseline for the study. Plant protection is implemented according to local practices (**Table 4**), and rows of single seeds are sown.
- **T2 – Extensive farming:** no plant protection is applied, and wide seed rows of 20 cm are implemented.
- **T3 – Diversified extensive farming:** no plant protection is applied, wide seed rows of 20 cm are implemented, and clover under-sowing is included.

2.6.6. Case study 14b (Finland): Contrasting minimum tillage and continuous plant cover with inversion tillage in wheat fields in boreal region

This study focuses on exploring the impact of different tillage practices on soil health within the context of organic farming. While traditional moldboard plowing has been widely used for weed control in organic agriculture, it has raised concerns about its potential negative effects on soil organisms and overall soil health (Peltoniemi et al., 2022). Minimum tillage is proposed as a crucial management practice to enhance biodiversity and improve soil functioning.

In this case study, two treatments were analyzed:

- **T1 – Intensive (control):** this represents traditional moldboard plowing, which is typically more disruptive to the soil.
- **T2 – Minimal (reduced tillage):** this practice involves reduced tillage, which is considered less disruptive to the soil.

In both treatments, organic agriculture practices were implemented, including the maintenance of continuous vegetation cover and the application of organic fertilizers, with no use of PPPs.

The first harvest year (2021) only wheat was produced, for the second harvest year (2022) wheat and peas were jointly produced and in the last harvest year (2023) only wheat was produced. The cover crops implemented were red clover and timothy.

3. Results

3.1. Environmental performance per case study

The following section provides an in-depth description of the environmental performance of each of the case studies conducted. Each case study is considered individually, with specific consideration given to the treatments tested.

3.1.1. Case study 1

➤ First cycle (potato)

Figure 6 and **Figure 7** present the environmental profile for potato cultivation, with one euro of gross margin and one hectare as the functional unit, respectively.

Based on 1 euro of gross margin, the results indicate that T1 exerts a more pronounced impact on the GW category, predominantly due to the extensive application of sheep manure. Moreover, T1 exhibits the most substantial impacts on SOD, TA, MR and FR, largely attributable to the application and production of mineral fertilizers. Moreover, T4 has the most significant impacts on FET, MET, TEC, FEC, MEC, LU and WU. This is attributable to the lower gross margin associated with T4 in comparison to the other treatments (18,869 €/ha). Conversely, T2 shows the best performance regardless of the impact category considered due to its higher profitability (21,268 €/ha). T3 remains between T2 and T4, since it has the second highest gross margin (20514 €/ha), except for TEC, in which it reports higher impact than in T1 due to the use of biological agent NUVE.

Figure 6: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 1 of the first year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

Upon examination of the environmental performance of potato cultivation per hectare, it was observed that the four treatments exhibited comparable performance in FET, MET, FEC, MEC, LU, and WU. The rationale behind this is that the same quantity of PPP and water for irrigation is used, as well as the same land area is cultivated. Moreover, a comparable quantity of fertilizers is applied. Additionally, T1 displays the most unfavorable results in terms of GW, SOD, TA, MR, and FR, while T2, T3, and T4 demonstrate comparable superior outcomes. This is attributable to the fact that T1 applies a higher dose of fertilizers.

Regarding the TEC, T3 is identified as the scenario with the most significant impact resulting from the application of the biological agent NUVE for pest control. The remaining scenarios are observed to demonstrate a comparable, albeit diminished, impact.

Figure 7: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 1 of the first year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Second cycle (broccoli)

With regard to the environmental profile of broccoli cultivation per euro of gross margin (**Figure 8**), T1 reports the highest impact on GW, SOD, TA, MR, and FR, despite having one of the highest profitability rates (3,300 €/ha), due to the application of the highest rate of mineral fertilizers. Furthermore, T3 and T4 demonstrate the highest environmental burdens with respect to FET, MET, FEC, MEC, and WU, attributable to the diminished profitability of T3 and T4 relative to T1 and T2 (3,317 €/ha for T2, 2,913 €/ha for T3 and 2,809 €/ha for T4).

T2 is the best treatment based on the economic FU, as its favorable yield and reduced costs (due to the lower quantity of inputs applied) result in greater profitability than the other four treatments.

Figure 8: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 1 of the second year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

Regarding the environmental performance per hectare of land managed (Figure 9), T1 reports the highest impact across impact categories except for FET, MET, TEC, FEC, MEC and LU. This is the result of the higher dose of fertilizers applied as part of this treatment.

Regarding FET, MET, FEC, MEC, and LU, all treatments exhibit comparable performance, as they occupy the same amount of land (LU) and apply the same amount of PPP (FEC, MEC). Furthermore, despite the higher application rate of fertilizers in T1, these differences do not result in a significant divergence in performance in FET and MET among the treatments. As in the potato cultivation cycle, T3 reports the highest impact in TEC due to the application of NUVE.

Figure 9: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 1 of the second year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Third cycle (melon)

As illustrated in **Figure 10**, the results based on the economic FU demonstrate that T1 exerts the most significant influence across all impact categories. This is due to the fact that T1 applies the highest dose of fertilizers, and it is the least profitable of the treatments in question (3,611 €/ha in T1, 3,696 €/ha in T2, 4,195 €/ha in T3 and 4,449 €/ha in T4). Despite generating one of the highest revenues, the higher doses of fertilizers applied result in higher costs, which ultimately offset the revenue gains.

Conversely, T4 is the most favorable treatment per economic FU, as it demonstrates the highest profitability and requires the application of fewer agrochemicals than T1. Furthermore, due to its higher gross margin, it exhibits superior performance in comparison to T2, which represents the treatment with the lowest impact per hectare.

Figure 10: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 1 of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

Regarding the land-based FU (Figure 11), T1 reports the highest environmental impacts on GW, SOD, TA, TEC, FEC, MEC, MR and FR due to the higher reliance on mineral fertilizers. In terms of FET, MET, and WU, all scenarios show comparable results, being slightly higher in T1 due to the higher fertilization rate. Additionally, all treatments exhibit the same impact on land use since the same area of land is occupied.

As in the previous cycles, T2 stands out as the most favorable treatment due to the lower dose of agrochemicals applied, followed by T3 and T4, where additional biological agents are used (Nuve and Bactoneco in T3 and T4, respectively).

Figure 11: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 1 of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Comparison between crops

When comparing the environmental performance of the three crop types, notable differences are observed. From the economic FU perspective (**Figure 12**), melon crop has the highest impact in 6 out of 12 impact categories (GW, SOD, TA, TEC, FR, WU). This is due to the higher impact associated with melon production and emphasized by the lower profitability compared to the potato cycle.

The cultivation of broccoli reports the highest impacts on FET, MET, MEC, LU and MR. This is attributed to the lowest profits obtained compared to the other crops, and in the case of FET, this is highlighted by its higher phosphorus emissions. In the case of potato, it shows the best performance across all impact categories, except for FEC, mainly due to the use of phytosanitary products.

Figure 12: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 1 of the crop rotation. Functional unit: 1€ of profit. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

From the perspective of land management FU (**Figure 13**), melon production has the highest impact on GW, SOD, TEC, FR and WU. This is a consequence of the higher doses of agrochemicals and biological agents applied, as well as the greater quantities of water used for irrigation.

Furthermore, the cycle with potato demonstrates the most significant impact on TA, MET, ecotoxicity-related impact categories, and MR, due to the incorporation of manure as a fertilizer, in conjunction with mineral fertilizers, as well as higher PPP. Moreover, all crops report similar impact in terms of LU.

In contrast, the broccoli cycle is the most environmentally favorable crop, only surpassing the other crops on FET due to higher phosphorus emissions due to higher Ser.

Figure 13: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 1 of the crop rotation. Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

3.1.2. Case study 4

➤ First cycle (potato)

The results vary depending on the FU considered. When the economic FU is used, T2 exhibits the greatest environmental impact (**Figure 14**). Conversely, when the land-based FU (1 hectare) is used, T1 shows the highest environmental impact per unit of land (**Figure 15**).

In economic terms, T2 is the least profitable treatment, followed by T1, T3 and T4. In contrast, T5 reports the highest gross margin. In this sense, the lower profitability of T2 makes it the most unfavorable treatment in terms of profitability per euro of gross margin. Conversely, the gross margin of T1 offsets its environmental load. Furthermore, the elevated profitability of T5 renders it the most advantageous treatment, surpassing T3 despite the latter's diminished impact per hectare.

On a land-management basis (**Figure 15**), the conventional treatment (T1) has the greatest environmental impact, largely due to its higher application rate of P fertilizers per hectare and the environmental consequences associated with their production. However, slight differences in environmental performance are observed among treatments, particularly in terms of GW, TA, FEC, MEC, FR and WU, due to slight differences in the doses applied. Regarding SOD, MET, and

LU, all scenarios exhibit comparable environmental performance due to the identical N-based fertilizer dose and the uniform amount of water utilized for irrigation.

Figure 14: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 4 of the first year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

T3, which does not include superphosphate fertilization or mycorrhiza, is identified as the most environmentally favorable treatment. Additionally, it is noteworthy that between T2 and T4 (which both utilize the same quantity of P fertilizers, but T2 does not include mycorrhiza and T4 does), T4 exhibits slightly higher environmental loads associated with the production of mycorrhiza and the additional field operation required.

Figure 15: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 4 of the first year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Second cycle (barley)

In the second cycle, barley is cultivated in a uniform manner across all plots, without any differentiated treatments. **Table 8** presents the absolute results for both FUs.

Table 8: Relative environmental characterization of case study (CS) 4 of the second year (Y). Functional unit: 1 € of profit and 1 ha.

Impact Category	Units	CS4-Y2 (FU: 1 €)	CS4-Y2 (FU: 1 ha)
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	1.36E+03	1.07E+03
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	5.97E-03	4.72E-03
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	9.06	7.16E
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	4.79E-01	3.78E-01
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	8.11E-01	6.41E-01
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.42E+03	1.12E+03
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.63	1.29E
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.74	1.38
Land use	m ² a crop eq	9.97E+03	7.88E+03
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	3.16E+01	2.49E+01
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	2.34E+02	1.85E+02
Water consumption	m ³	3.82E+01	3.02E+01

➤ Third cycle (potato)

Figure 16 and **Figure 17** displays the environmental performance of the third cycle of the rotation based on an economic and land management functional unit.

From an economic FU perspective, T4 is associated with the most significant environmental impacts in comparison to the other treatments. This is attributed to the low yield per area and the poor profitability of the treatment, which results in higher resource consumption and emissions per unit of output. Similarly, T2 also displays an unfavorable environmental profile, attributable to the same underlying factors.

Conversely, T1 and T3 are the most optimal solutions in terms of both environmental performance and profitability. The higher yields and superior economic returns partially offset their environmental load, thereby rendering them more sustainable options per euro of gross margin.

Figure 16: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 4 of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

In the hectare-based analysis, a comparable environmental profile is observed for the third cycle of potato cultivation, although the differences between treatments are less pronounced than in the first cycle. This is likely due to the lower fertilizer dose applied in the third cycle. In this regard, all treatments demonstrate comparable outcomes across the spectrum of impact categories, particularly with regard to SOD, TA, MET, FEC, MEC, LU, and WU, given that the same

operational procedures are carried out, with the exception of fertilization and pest control, where slight discrepancies exist in the applied dose and the utilization of mycorrhiza, respectively. Moreover, since T1 applies the largest dose of mineral fertilizers, it presents a greater impact on FET.

T3 and T5 exhibit the lowest values in FET due to the absence of P fertilizer application. T5 demonstrates the lowest score in TEC, attributed to the lack of phosphorus fertilization and the absence of mycorrhizal utilization. T3 shows the lowest value in MR and FR, with the most significant difference observed among the treatments owing to fewer field operations.

Figure 17: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 4 of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Comparison between crops

When comparing crops, the barley cycle reports the highest environmental impact per euro of gross margin, while the least per hectare.

Given that barley exhibits the lowest gross margin, it displays a markedly superior environmental impact when evaluated based on the economic FU (**Figure 18**). In contrast, potatoes generate significant profits in the first and third production cycles (between €5,923 and €14,511 per hectare), resulting in a more favorable environmental profile compared to barley. Furthermore, the potato crop of the third year exhibits the most favorable environmental profile, primarily

due to its superior profitability, but also due to the lower environmental loads per hectare observed in numerous impact categories.

Figure 18: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 4 of the crop rotation. Functional unit: 1€ of profit. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

In the case of the functional unit of 1 hectare (**Figure 19**), barley presents the least environmental impact among the three crops, primarily due to the lower quantity of agrochemicals applied per hectare. The cultivation of potato has a similar environmental profile in both years across all impact categories, except for TEC, FEC, MEC, MR, FR and WU. In all these impact categories the third cycle performs better than the first one, except for WU, in which the first cycle outperforms the third cycle. This is attributed to the higher usage of PPP per hectare in the first cycle (TEC, FEC, MEC), and to the higher field operations frequency and slightly higher fertilizer dosage applied (MR, FR). In contrast, the third cycle consumes the highest quantity of water, which leads to the most significant impact in WU.

Figure 19: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 4 of the crop rotation. Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

3.1.3. Case study 8

➤ First cycle (leek)

In the profit-based analysis (**Figure 20**), T1 and T2 have the highest impacts on TEC, FEC, MEC, LU, MR, FR and WU, as well as on MET (together with T3), due to their lower profitability compared to T3 and T4, together with their higher impact per hectare for some impact categories (FEC, MEC, LU, MR, FR). Conversely, T4 has the best environmental impact for most of the impact categories (FET, MET, TEC, FEC, MEC, LU, MR, FR, WU) due to its higher profitability and low impact per hectare FU.

However, despite the high economic profitability of T3, this treatment has the highest environmental impact on GW, SOD, TA and MET due to its significantly higher impact on these impact categories related to the higher dose of organic fertilizer (e.g. cattle manure).

Figure 20: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 8 of the first year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

Concerning the land-based analysis (**Figure 21**), shows that T3 has the highest environmental impacts in GW, SOD, TA, MET and TEC. These impacts are mainly due to the significantly higher use of cattle manure as fertilizer. T2 has higher impacts in FEC, MEC, LU, MR and FR due to the use of green manure, mineral fertilizers and PPP. In terms of FET, T1 and T3 perform worse due to higher phosphorus emissions from fertilization.

Regarding MEC and WU, all treatments show a similar environmental performance. T1 and T2 stand out with the best environmental performance in 4 out of 12 impact categories (GW, SOD, TA, MET). In addition, T3 and T4 show the best performance in 4 impact categories: FEC, LU, MR, FR. In terms of TEC, T4 performs best.

There is no clear-cut treatment that stands out as more environmentally friendly, so the preference for a specific treatment will ultimately depend on which impact categories are prioritized.

Figure 21: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 8 of the first year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Second cycle (celery)

There is a noticeable difference between the two analyses. In the first analysis, based on economic yield (**Figure 22**), T2 shows a significant higher environmental impact compared to the other treatments due to the notable lower profit of T2 (283 €/ha) and its higher impact per hectare in most impact categories. Among the remaining treatments, T3 stands out as the most impactful across most impact categories, except for SOD and TEC, in which T1 also leads the impact.

Figure 22: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 8 of the second year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

Considering the land-based FU (**Figure 23**), T2 exhibits the greatest impact on 9 out of 12 impact categories (GW, SOD, TA, MET, FEC, MR, FR and WU). This is mainly attributed to the higher quantities of diesel, seeds and organic fertilizer used. T3 has the greatest impact on FET, primarily due to the high amount of organic fertilizer applied along with the use of conventional tillage, which disturbs the soil more and increases phosphorus leaching to freshwater, exacerbated by the amount of organic fertilizer applied per hectare. T4, on the other hand, applies the same amount of organic fertilizer per hectare, but uses reduced tillage, resulting in lower impact compared to T3.

In terms of LU, all treatments perform equally, except for T1, which shows a lower environmental load due to the lower quantity of seeds linked to the absence of cover crops.

Figure 23: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 8 of the second year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Third cycle (cauliflower)

Considering the economic FU perspective (**Figure 24**), T4 exhibits the lowest environmental impacts across all impact categories, except for MR, in which T3 excels, due to its higher economic profitability and lower environmental loads per hectare in some impact categories. Although T3 follows closely in terms of profitability, it presents greater impacts due to the significantly higher doses of farmyard cattle manure in T3 leading to higher nitrogen emissions into the environment compared to those of green compost applied in T2 and T4.

T2, being the least profitable treatment, shows the most significant impact in several categories, including MET, TEC, FEC, MEC, LU, MR, FR and WU. T1, although having a slightly lower environmental footprint than T2, shows the greatest impact in the FET due to the use of urea as a mineral fertilizer.

Figure 24: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 8 of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

When evaluating the environmental impacts considering the land-based FU (**Figure 25**), T3 reports the largest impact in 7 out of the 12 impact categories (GW, SOD, TA, FET, MET, TEC and MEC). This is attributed to the significantly higher application dose of farmyard manure, which generates emissions during its production and after its application, as well as due to the significantly higher diesel consumption linked to higher fertilization frequency. Moreover, T2 exhibits a greater impact in 5 out of the 12 impact categories, affecting FEC, LU, MR, FR and WU, mainly due to the higher dose of seeds applied. Conversely, T4 is the treatment that performs best on a greater number of impact categories, including GW, SOD, TA, FET, MET and FEC, while T1 does it on TEC, MEC and LU, and T3 on MR and FR.

Figure 25: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 8 of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Comparison between crops

Differences emerge depending on the FU considered. In **Figure 26**, which depicts the environmental profile under the economic FU, celery stands out as having the highest environmental impacts across all impact categories, exceeding those of leek and cauliflower by up to 60%. This is largely due to celery's lower economic return due to the lower production levels compared to the other crops, leading to higher environmental burdens per euro of gross margin.

In contrast, when considering the analysis based on the managed area (**Figure 27**), leek displays the highest impacts on GW, SOD, TA, MET, MEC, MR, and WU, due to its higher reliance on organic and mineral fertilizers. Celery shows higher impacts in FET, TEC, FEC, LU and FR, as it uses larger quantities of conventional seeds and more green compost, which demands additional land. Cauliflower stands out as the least environmentally impactful of the three crops.

Figure 26: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 8 of the crop rotation. Functional unit: 1€ of profit. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

Figure 27: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 8 of the crop rotation. Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

3.1.4. Case study 9

➤ First cycle (wheat)

In the first cycle, wheat is cultivated uniformly across all plots without any differentiated treatments. In **Table 9**, the economic analysis shows less impact compared to the analysis based on cultivated area. In this case, the impact in the economic analysis may seem less pronounced when economic gains are involved, as financial profit tends to smooth out environmental impacts, potentially obscuring visible effects. Conversely, the analysis based on cultivated area offers a more tangible and direct view of land use and input applications per hectare, making environmental impacts more apparent.

Table 9: Relative environmental characterization of case study (CS) 9 for the first cycle (Y). Functional unit: 1 € of profit and 1 ha.

Impact Category	Units	CS9-Y1 (FU: 1 €)	CS9-Y1 (FU: 1 ha)
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	2.09E+00	7.61E+02
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	1.64E-05	5.99E-03
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	8.77E-03	3.20E+00
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	4.97E-04	1.81E-01
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	2.53E-02	9.25E+00
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.52E	5.55E+02
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	8.47E-04	3.09E-01
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.41E-03	5.15E-01
Land use	m ² a crop eq	2.29E+01	8.36E+03
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	1.57E-02	5.72E+00
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	2.42E-01	8.81E+01
Water consumption	m ³	9.34E-02	3.41E+01

➤ Second cycle (wheat)

In the economic analysis (**Figure 28**), a clear distinction emerges between the different treatments, particularly highlighting T3 and T4. These treatments show economic losses, meaning a larger quantity of wheat must be produced to generate profits, unlike T1 and T2, which are more economically viable.

T3 is particularly noteworthy, as it exhibits the greatest environmental impact across all categories compared to the other treatments, followed closely by T2. In contrast, T4 emerges as the treatment with the lowest overall impacts, making it the most environmentally sustainable choice.

Figure 28: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 9 of the second year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

Per land-based FU (**Figure 29**), T1 shows greater impacts on GW, SOD, TA, and MET. This is attributed to the use of farmyard manure, which results in higher nitrogen emissions compared to the fertilizers used in the other treatments, such as compost in T2, fermented organic material in T3, and the absence of fertilizer in T4.

T3 results in higher impacts in the remaining impact categories (e.g., FET, TEC, FEC, MEC, MR and FR), due to its higher diesel consumption per area. In contrast, T4 is the most favorable treatment, using the least amount of diesel per hectare and not applying any fertilizers.

Figure 29: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 9 of the second year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Third cycle (potato)

In the case of potato cultivation, both the economic (**Figure 30**) and area-based (**Figure 31**) analyses give similar results. T1 consistently shows the highest environmental impact across the different impact categories, including GW, SOD, TA and ME. This is largely due to the use of farmyard manure, the production of which is associated with higher emissions than the other organic fertilizers analyzed that contribute to these impacts. In addition, T3 has the most notorious impact on FET, TEC, FEC, MEC, MR, FR, LU and WU due to the use of grass silage as fertilizer and higher diesel consumption.

T2 and T4 show the best performance regardless of FU. The reason for these results is that T4 does not use organic fertilizers and therefore has lower emissions associated with their production and application, and both have low environmental burns associated with field operations.

Figure 30: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 9 of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

Figure 31: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 9 of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Comparison between crops

A comparison of the environmental performance of different crops reveals that the second year of wheat cultivation exhibits a comparatively lower economic profitability, resulting in a markedly higher environmental performance per € of gross margin in comparison to the first (wheat) and third (potato) years (**Figure 32**).

Figure 32: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 9 of the crop rotation. Functional unit: 1€ of profit. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

When evaluating the impacts per hectare of land managed (**Figure 33**), there is a notable difference in environmental impacts between crops and years. In year one, wheat uses fewer inputs per hectare than in years two and three, resulting in lower impacts in all categories.

In the second year (wheat), there is a significant increase in the FET and WU impacts, mainly due to the increased use of organic fertilizers. This increase is attributed to the use of different types of organic fertilizers, which contribute to higher emissions and resource consumption per hectare.

In contrast, potato production in year 3 has the highest impacts in most categories (GW, SOD, TA, MET, TEC, FEC, MEC, LU, MR and FR), mainly due to the high diesel consumption and seed use.

Figure 33: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 9 of the crop rotation. Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

3.1.5. Case study 11

➤ First cycle (wheat)

As illustrated in **Figure 34**, T1 demonstrates the most significant impact across all categories, except for MET and LU, due to its reliance on PPP. It is notable that these elevated environmental loads are particularly pronounced in ecotoxicity-related impact categories (e.g., MEC and FEC), reflecting the environmental impact associated with the production of PPP. In contrast, T3 exhibits the greatest environmental impact on MET and LU, attributable to the elevated seed dosage. Except for MEC and FEC, the three treatments demonstrate comparable results, which can be explained by the fact that all treatments apply the same mineral fertilizer rate and have a similar diesel consumption.

Figure 34: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 11 of the first year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Second cycle (maize)

In the second cycle, **Figure 35**, all treatments demonstrate identical impacts across all categories, apart from GW, due to the absence of differentiation between treatments and thus, the implementation of identical cultivation practices. The observed variation on GW can be primarily attributed to the amount of carbon sequestered in the soil. The T2 treatment captured the greatest amount of carbon, followed by T1 and T3.

Figure 35: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 11 of the second year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Third cycle (wheat)

As in the second cycle, the treatments do not align with the defined treatments (e.g., control, extensive farming and diversified extensive farming), as the same PPP dosage is applied, and clover is not incorporated in T3. This explains the similar environmental performance obtained among treatments (**Figure 36**), with the primary distinction being in GW due to variations in carbon sequestration among field plots. The difference observed in the global warming category is attributed to the practices employed in this treatment, particularly crop rotation, which minimize soil disturbance and contribute to an increase in soil organic matter (Hartmann & Six, 2022b). T2 has the least impact in this category, followed by T3 and T4.

Figure 36: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 11 of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Comparison between crops

In the **Figure 37**, wheat in year 1 exhibits higher impacts in TA and TEC, primarily due to emissions from the application of ammonium sulfate. Maize cultivation in year 2 shows the most significant impacts across categories such as GW, SOD, FET, MET, LU and FR, as it utilizes the highest amount of mineral fertilizer per hectare, and the application of sulfur and silica also contributes to these impacts. Finally, wheat has greater impacts in FEC, MEC, MR and WU due to its increased use of PPP and diesel per hectare.

Figure 37: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 11 of the crop rotation. Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

3.1.6. Case study 14b

➤ First cycle (wheat)

From an economic point of view (**Figure 38**), T2 is identified as the treatment with the largest impact, mainly due to its lower profitability resulting from lower yields compared to T1. Considering that both scenarios have similar environmental impacts per hectare, the lower profitability of T2 results in higher environmental impacts per euro of gross margin. However, this is not the case for FE, in which the higher profitability of T1 does not compensate for the higher environmental impact of T1 on FET.

Considering the land-based FU (**Figure 39**), T1 and T2 show similar results, with significant differences only for GW and FET. For GW, T1 has a lower environmental impact than T2, even with higher diesel consumption and conventional tillage, due to the higher biomass input of T1. In terms of FET, T1 has a higher impact due to higher diesel consumption and the use of conventional tillage, which tends to disturb the soil more, increasing phosphorus leaching to freshwater.

Figure 38: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 14b of the first year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

Figure 39: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 14b of the first year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Second cycle (pea)

From an economic point of view (**Figure 40**) T2 emerges as the least environmentally friendly option, mainly due to the lower yield of T2, which leads to higher environmental impacts per euro of gross margin, considering that both treatments have similar environmental profile per hectare of cultivated area. In the area-based analysis (**Figure 41**), the environmental impacts of the two treatments are comparable, since they carry out the same agricultural activities, except for the type of tillage applied (conventional plowing in T1 and reduced tillage in T2), which does not lead to a difference in environmental loads, with the exception of FET. In this sense, in terms of FET, T1 has a higher environmental impact regardless of the FU considered, due to the higher phosphorus runoff to freshwater bodies in T1 associated with the application of conventional plowing.

Furthermore, the slight difference in the GW profile between treatments can be explained by the differences in carbon sequestration, with T1 sequestering more carbon per hectare than T2, due to the greater biomass input.

Figure 40: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 14b of the second year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

Figure 41: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 14b of the second year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Third cycle (wheat)

In the third cycle, T1 stands out as the most impactful treatment regardless of the FU considered (**Figure 42**, **Figure 43**), although the differences in environmental impact are more pronounced per euro of gross margin (**Figure 42**) due to the lower yield achieved by T1 (1,402 kg per plot versus 1,894 kg in T2). Additionally, T1 presents greater environmental burden on GW due to the higher amount of diesel used, and on FET, due to the implementation of conventional tillage, leading to higher phosphorus emissions into water bodies.

Figure 42: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 14b of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

Figure 43: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 14b of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Comparison between crops

There are several similarities between the environmental profile per economic and managed area FU, as shown in **Figure 44** and **Figure 45**. In both profiles, the first cycle of wheat shows significant impacts on TA and MR, mainly due to the higher diesel consumption and the application of organic fertilizer. Similarly, pea shows the highest impact on the ecotoxicity related impact categories, largely due to the higher dosage of seed applied.

A notable similarity is seen with third cycle wheat, which has relatively high environmental impacts on GW, SOD and WU. This is probably due to the high diesel consumption and the application of mineral fertilizers.

In terms of economic yield, the crops have similar yields, so the main factor influencing the differences in environmental impacts is the quantity of inputs used per hectare, which varies between the crop cycles.

Figure 44: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 14b of the crop rotation. Functional unit: 1€ of profit. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

Figure 45: Relative environmental impact of case study (CS) 14b of the crop rotation. Functional unit: 1 ha. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

3.2. Main factors contributing to the environmental profile per case study

3.2.1. Case study 1

➤ First cycle (potato)

In **Figure 46**, the study highlights that field emissions are the main contributor to the environmental impact of FET and MET, accounting for approximately 90% of the total impact, largely due to the application of nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizers. In addition, both seed and field emissions contribute to TEC (72% from seeds), FEC (30% from seeds and 60% from field emissions), and MEC (60% from seed and 30% from field emissions) due to their association with the application of PPPs. The active ingredients in these PPPs can reduce the mobility, growth and reproduction of essential soil organisms such as microbes, earthworms and insects. These organisms are critical for nutrient cycling, decomposition, and maintenance of soil structure (Hartmann & Six, 2022a).

For T3 and T4, the use of specific products such as Nuve and Bactoneco appears to have minimal impact on these impact categories, at 2% and 1%, respectively. This suggests that while field emissions from fertilizers and pesticides have a significant impact on the environmental

footprint, the use of these products in the specified treatments has a relatively minor role in exacerbating impacts within these categories.

Figure 46: Impact contribution per factor for case study 1 of the first year of the crop rotation. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Second cycle (broccoli)

Most of the impacts for this second cycle study (Figure 47) are associated with the use of mineral fertilizers, which play a dominant role in several categories. These N and P fertilizers account for more than 90% of the impacts on the SOD, TET, MET, FEC and MEC categories. In addition, the production of these mineral fertilizers contributes significantly to MR, with about 80% of the impacts.

The use of diesel in field operations also has a significant environmental impact, particularly on TEC, where it contributes around 80% of the impacts. Diesel consumption also has a significant impact on FR, accounting for more than 50% of the impacts in this category.

Figure 47: Impact contribution per factor for case study 1 of the second year of the crop rotation. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Third cycle (melon)

Figure 48 shows that most emissions in the categories of stratospheric ozone depletion (90%), terrestrial acidification (37%), freshwater eutrophication (86%), marine eutrophication (99%), and freshwater ecotoxicity (69%) are primarily associated with field emissions directly related to the application of N and P mineral fertilizers.

Field operations also contribute significantly to the GW (56%), TEC (42%), MEC (50%), MR (52%), and FR (about 65%) categories. These impacts are largely driven by the use of diesel in machinery used in agricultural activities. In addition, the production of mineral fertilizers contributes to the impacts in the TEC (47%) and MEC (20%) categories, highlighting the environmental impact associated not only with their use, but also with their production.

Figure 48: Impact contribution per factor for case study 1 of the third year of the crop rotation. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

3.2.2. Case study 4

➤ First cycle (potato)

As shown in **Figure 62**, most of the environmental impacts are driven by field emissions associated with the use of mineral fertilizers and PPP, particularly in the categories of GW (about 30%), SOD (over 80%), TA (about 50%), FEC (about 50%), TET (over 60%), and MET (over 90%). The extensive use of N fertilizers contributes to GW and SOD due to the release of nitrous oxide. Meanwhile, both N and P fertilizers significantly affect FET and MET due to nutrient leaching and runoff.

In addition, the seeds used also have a significant environmental impact, especially in TEC (about 50%), FEC (about 40%) and MEC (about 90%). This is largely due to the common practice of using PPP in the production of commercial seeds, which, depending on the concentration, may have harmful effects on both the environment and organisms (Beaumelle et al., 2023). The production of mineral fertilizers also contributes to MR (40%) and FR (40%). Similarly, the use of diesel in field operations affects MR and FR (40% and 30%, respectively).

The use of water for irrigation also plays a major role in WU, with about 80% of the impact directly related to irrigation practices. Finally, the application of mycorrhiza has no significant impact on treatments T3 and T4.

➤ Second cycle (barley)

There is no differentiation between treatments in this cycle. As illustrated in **Figure 49**, a large portion of the environmental impacts are related to field operations, particularly the use of diesel in machinery. This has a significant impact on several impact categories, contributing to 73% of the GW impact, 52% of the TA, 62% of the TET, 57% of the MET and 70% of the FR.

Field emissions resulting from the use of mineral fertilizers and the application of PPP have a significant impact on SOD (64%), FET (87%) and FEC (57%).

In the case of MET, the largest impact comes from seeds (61%), mainly because the production of commercial seeds involves the use of fertilizers and significant amounts of water, as reflected in WU (87%). Finally, the production of mineral fertilizers contributes significantly to MR (73%).

Figure 49: Impact contribution per factor for case study (CS) 4 of the second year of the crop rotation. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Third cycle (potato)

As shown in **Figure 63**, field emissions contribute significantly to five major environmental impact categories: GW (30%), SOD (over 80%), TA (over 55%), TET (over 70%), and MET (over 90%). These impacts are primarily driven by the release of ammonia and nitrous oxide during N fertilizer application, which increases terrestrial acidification. Ammonia also plays a critical role in eutrophication, along with P fertilizers, which exacerbate eutrophication through runoff and leaching. In addition, PPPs contribute to ecotoxicity by adversely affecting the environment and wildlife.

The application of seeds also has a significant impact, particularly on terrestrial ecotoxicity (50%), FEC (80%) and MEC (90%). This is due to the heavy reliance on PPPs in commercial seed production.

In addition, diesel consumption in field operations and the use of mineral fertilizers contribute significantly to MR (40% each) and FR (25% and 40%, respectively).

3.2.3. Case study 8

➤ First cycle (leek)

Most emissions in this study (**Figure 50**) are primarily associated with fertilizer application in the field and seed use. For T1 and T2, the impacts are mainly due to the use of commercial seeds, which contribute significantly to GW, SOD, MEC and WU. In addition, the use of diesel in the field plays an important role in TEC and FR. As these two treatments rely on mineral fertilizers, they also have significant impacts on MR.

In terms of land use, T2 shows a small percentage impact for fertilizers because green compost requires additional land to obtain compost material. For T3 and T4, which use cattle slurry and farmyard manure - fertilizers with higher nitrogen content - there are higher nitrogen emissions, leading to increased impacts on GW, SOD, TA and MET. The use of diesel in these treatments also affects TEC and TR due to their dependence on field operations. In addition, the use of commercial seed in T3 and T4 further contributes to impacts on FEC, MEC, FR and WU.

Figure 50: Impact contribution per factor for case study 8 of the first year of the crop rotation. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Second cycle (celery)

In **Figure 51**, we observe that field emissions from organic fertilizers (T2, T3, and T4) and emissions from mineral fertilizers (T1) cause significant impacts on SOD, TET and MET. Notably, in the SOD category, the absence of mineral fertilizers in T3 and T4 leads to a reduction of field emissions by up to 20% compared to T1 and T2. However, this reduction results in increased impacts in other categories. For instance, in LU, more than 30% of the impacts arise from the land required to cultivate green compost. Similarly, the impacts on MR (around 70%), FR (around 40%), and WU (around 30%) are associated with the use of green compost.

Field operations also play a significant role in all treatments, contributing to impacts on GW, TA, TEC, MEC, MR and FR, largely due to the use of diesel during field operations. Additionally, seeds remain a major contributor, particularly in the categories of TEC (more than 60%), FEC (more than 80% for T3 and T4), MEC (more than 50%), and WU (around 50%).

Figure 51: Impact contribution per factor for case study 8 of the second year of the crop rotation. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Third cycle (cauliflower)

In the **Figure 52** for the T3 case, the use of cow manure is a major contributor to the environmental impacts related to nitrogen emissions, particularly to GW, SOD, and TA, with impacts exceeding 80%. In addition, phosphorus emissions from manure contribute significantly to MET, accounting for over 50% of the impacts.

Field emissions (related to the use of fertilizers and PPP) also play a crucial role for SOD and TA impacts for T1 and T2, with contributions of around 80%, and for FET and MET, with contributions of more than 50%. It's worth noting that in T4 a reduction in GHG emissions on GW is observed, which is attributed to carbon sequestration based on the analyzed soil carbon data. Soil carbon sequestration results in a modest 2% reduction in field emissions. According to FAO, practices implemented in this case study, such as reduced tillage, cover crops, and crop rotations that minimize soil disturbance, can effectively enhance carbon sequestration. These practices help soil ecosystems maintain essential services such as erosion control, water retention, nutrient cycling, and improved soil fertility (FAO, 2019).

The application of green compost in T2 and T4 contributes 20% of the impacts in the land use category, reflecting the area required for compost production. Meanwhile, the use of diesel for

field operations contributes to GW (20%), TEC (40%), MEC (40%), and MR and FR (over 20% each).

In addition, seed use has a significant impact on FEC (40%) and WU, contributing more than 80% of the impacts in these categories. The production of PPP also plays a role, contributing about 10% of the impacts in T1 and T2 in different impact categories.

Figure 52: Impact contribution per factors for case study 8 of the third year of the crop rotation. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

3.2.4. Case Study 9

➤ First cycle (wheat)

Analyzing the contributions (**Figure 53**), it is clear that the largest share of environmental impacts comes from field operations, specifically the machinery and diesel used for land preparation, seeding, fertilizing, and harvesting wheat. These operations have a significant impact on several categories: GW (65%), TA (70%), FET (90%), MET (79%), TEC (91%), FEC (65%), MR (93%), and WU (82%).

In addition, field emissions have significant contributions to SOD (65%) and MEC (48%). Seed use contributes significantly to FR, accounting for 62% of the impact. Finally, land use is the most relevant factor for LU, contributing 97% of the impacts in this category.

Figure 53: Impact contribution per factor for case study (CS) 9 of the first year of the crop rotation. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Second cycle (wheat)

The contribution breakdown (**Figure 54**) for the different treatments shows that: in T1, most of emissions come from farmyard manure, which is responsible for more than 90% of the impacts in categories such as GW, SOD, TA, and MET. For T2, T3 and T4, field operations contribute significantly with over 40% of the impacts on GW and about 30% on TA. Field operations also affect all treatments on TEC, where they account for 80% of the impacts, MEC (60%), MR (about 80% for T1 and T2, and 40% for T3 and T4), and FR (70% for T1 and T2, and 40% for T3 and T4). The use of seeds plays a key role, contributing 50% to FET, 50% to FEC and 90% to WU for all treatments.

For T2, a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions was observed, due to carbon sequestration. This reduction can be linked to the practices used in this treatment, such as reduced tillage, cover crops, and crop rotation, which are less disruptive to soil structure. These practices not only enhance ecosystem services by increasing soil organic matter, but also preserve soil

structure, ensuring that microbial processes remain largely unaffected, thereby supporting the integrity of soil ecosystems (Hartmann & Six, 2022b). However, field emissions from organic fertilizer application (T2, T3, and T4) contributes about 90% of the impact on MET. In terms of land use, land occupation is the most relevant factor, contributing 90% of the impacts for T1, T2 and T4. In T3, the use of fermented plant material, which requires additional land, contributes 20% to land use impact.

Figure 54: Impact contribution per factors for case study 9 of the second year of the crop rotation. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Third cycle (potato)

In the **Figure 55**, T1 exhibits notable impacts on GW, SOD, TA, and MET due to the use of farmyard manure as fertilizer. These impacts are driven by the higher nitrogen emissions associated with this type of manure. T3 shows significant impacts on MR, FR and WU, which are linked to the application of fermented organic material used as fertilizer.

The use of diesel plays a critical role in T2, T3, and T4, where it contributes around 80% of the impact on GW and 70% on TA due to field operations. On MR, FR, and WU

In the categories of mineral resource scarcity, fossil resource scarcity, and water use, field operations also contribute more than 70% of the impacts for T1, T2, and T4, primarily due to machinery use and fuel consumption during land preparation and other processes.

The use of diesel in field operations impacts GW, FR, contributing approximately 30% to these categories. Seeds contribute between 30% and 50% for MR and around 55% for WU. Furthermore, land occupation plays a dominant role in LU, with a contribution of approximately 95% across all treatments, while seeds contribute the remaining 5%.

Figure 56: Impact contribution per factor for case study 11 of the first year of the crop rotation. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Second cycle (maize)

It can be observed (Figure 57) that GW impact is distributed across several factors: field emissions contribute 20%, field operations account for 20%, fertilizer production makes up 25%, and PPP production contributes 30%.

Field emissions dominate in SOD with 91%, TA with 40%, and both FEC and MET with 97%, primarily due to the application of mineral fertilizers. PPP production plays a major role in the categories of TEC (65%), FEC (67%), MEC (56%), MR (43%), and FR (43%). Fertilizer production significantly contributes to MR and FR (51% and 47% respectively), and WU (89%). Diesel use in field operations has a minor but notable contribution to TA (16%), TEC (21%), and MEC (27%). Furthermore, land occupation remains overwhelmingly significant in LU with a 99% contribution.

Figure 57: Impact contribution per factors for case study 11 of the second of the crop rotation. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Third cycle (wheat)

The contributions in **Figure 58** show that field emissions from mineral fertilizers and plant protection products (PPP) are the main drivers of environmental impacts, contributing significantly to GW (30%), SOD (82%), TA (59%), and ecotoxicity-related impact categories (over 90% for FEC, MEC, TEC).

Fertilizer production also plays a key role, especially in TEC (77%), FR (66%), and WU (31%). PPP production is notable for its contribution to MR (31%), while seeds add impacts in both MR (43%) and WU (67%). Field operations further contribute to GW (33%) and FR (20%). Regarding LU, 95% of the impact stems from land occupation, with seeds accounting for the remaining 5%.

Figure 58: Impact contribution per factors for case study 11 of the third of the crop rotation. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

3.2.6. Case study 14b

➤ First cycle (wheat)

As shown in **Figure 59**, there is a substantial reduction of GW impact due to carbon sequestration. T1 demonstrates a more significant reduction of 36% compared to T2 at 21%. The process of soil carbon sequestration enhances organic content, thereby improving soil structure, water retention, and nutrient availability. These enhancements support ecosystems in maintaining essential services such as food production and water purification (Corsi et al., 2012).

Field emissions from organic fertilizers contribute significantly to TEC, accounting for more than 60%, and to MET at 75%. Seeds also play an important role, contributing 79% to SOD, 44% to TA, 68% to FEC, and 97% to WU.

Field operations impact several categories, contributing 50% to GW, 56% to TA, 85% to TEC, 71% to MEC, 84% to MR, and 69% to FR. Finally, land occupation is responsible for 92% of the impacts in the LU category.

Figure 59: Impact contribution per factors for case study 14b of the first of the crop rotation. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Second cycle (pea)

In **Figure 60** similar to the previous crop, soil carbon sequestration (approximately 20%) reduces CO₂ emissions from the field, leading to a decreased impact on GW. This demonstrates that this practice can enhance the soil's role as a net carbon sink, helping soil ecosystems sequester more carbon over time.

Field emissions in categories like FEC (92%) and MET (58%) are mainly caused by phosphorus emissions from water erosion, run-off, and leaching into water sources.

Seeds also make significant contributions to several impact categories, including GW (53%), SOD (75%), TA (44%), TEC (94%), FEC (99%), and MEC (99%). Meanwhile, field operations contribute notably to GW (40%) and TA (56%). Land occupation remains a major factor on LU impact, accounting for 90% of the environmental load.

Figure 60: Impact contribution per factors for case study 14b of the second of the crop rotation. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

➤ Third cycle (wheat)

In **Figure 61**, it can be observed that seeds play a significant role in contributing to environmental impacts, particularly in the categories of GW (27%), SOD (84%), TA (66%), FET (17%), MET (34%), TEC (61%), FEC (93%), MEC (76%), MR (100%), FR (82%), and WU (100%).

The second major factor is field emissions, where T1 has a higher impact on GW (49%) compared to T2 (40%) due to greater carbon sequestration in T2's soil. For FET and MET, field emissions contribute around 66%, but T1 shows higher impacts (83%) due to conventional tillage, which increases phosphorus emissions into freshwater bodies.

Field operations are also relevant in GW (26%), TA (34%), TEC (25%), MEC (20%), and FR (18% for T1 and 8% for T2, as T1 uses more diesel per hectare). Lastly, land occupation accounts for 89% of the impact on LU.

Figure 61: Impact contribution per factors for case study 14b of the third of the crop rotation. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

3.2.7. Soil, ecosystem services and biodiversity

As outlined in the project objectives, SoildiverAgro aims to enhance agricultural sustainability through diverse cultivation practices, particularly focusing on reducing greenhouse gas emissions. The project also seeks to identify and quantify the relationships between soil biodiversity and the ecosystem services it provides.

Soils are a vital reservoir of biodiversity, playing a key role in storing, filtering, and transforming nutrients, substances, and water. Through the process of soil carbon cycling, soils can function as a carbon sink, which is essential for regulating various ecosystem services and mitigating GHG in the atmosphere (Anikwe & Ife, 2023). Key soil ecosystem services include erosion control, support for biodiversity, water retention, nutrient cycling, and improved soil fertility—all of which contribute to the overall health of ecosystems (Masciandaro et al., 2018).

Shifting agricultural land management to other types of practices, such as those that disturb the soil less (like reduced tillage), use cover crops, limit the use of PPP, and implement crop rotation, can be effective in providing a net carbon sink in soils, meaning they can help soil ecosystems increase the sequestration of more carbon (FAO, 2017). As seen in cases **CS8**, **CS9**, and **CS14b**, the use of these practices not only boosts soil carbon sequestration and enhances ecosystem services by increasing soil organic matter, but also preserves soil structure, ensuring that

microbial processes remain largely unchanged. This, in turn, helps maintain the integrity of soil ecosystems (Hartmann & Six, 2022b).

4. Conclusions

Six case studies of crop management practices were evaluated using life cycle assessment methodology to compare their environmental performance and identify the most sustainable options. These case studies were conducted over three years in five different climatic zones. In each case study, different treatments were tested, including crop rotation, organic farming, different tillage practices, and nutrient applications. Two functional units were chosen for the environmental analysis: an economic FU (1 € of gross margin) and a land-based FU (1 ha of cropland).

Significant differences in environmental performance were observed depending on the FU considered. The economic FU smoothed the environmental impact of the treatments with the highest profits and worsened the environmental profile of those with lower gross margins, as seen in cases like year 2 of CS4 and CS9.

Impact categories such as global warming, stratospheric ozone depletion, terrestrial acidification, terrestrial eutrophication, and marine eutrophication were highly sensitive to fertilizer type, as shown in case studies CS1, CS4, CS8, CS9, CS11, and CS14b. Nitrogen fertilizers contributed significantly to global warming and stratospheric ozone depletion through the release of nitrous oxide. These fertilizers also contributed to acidification through emissions of nitrous oxide and ammonia and were major contributors to eutrophication in freshwater and marine ecosystems through emissions of nitrate and ammonia. Conversely, phosphorus fertilizers had a greater impact on freshwater eutrophication through phosphorus emissions. The vulnerability of these categories to tillage was notable in CS14b, where conventional tillage emphasized soil erosion and phosphorus runoff.

In case studies CS8 and CS9, liquid manure, with its higher nitrogen and phosphorus content, resulted in more emissions than solid manure. Animal manure generally produced more nitrogen and phosphorus emissions than green manure, although compost and fermented plant material required more land for their production. Mineral fertilizers also showed notable differences compared to organic fertilizers. While contributing to categories such as mineral resource depletion, global warming, stratospheric ozone depletion, and terrestrial acidification, mineral fertilizers had a lower overall impact due to their lower application rates per hectare, as shown in Case Studies CS1, CS8, CS9, and CS14b.

The acquisition of commercial seeds also broadly contributed to several impact categories due to the inputs involved in their production, such as fertilizers and pesticides, which contributed to a wide range of environmental impacts across the studied categories.

In case studies CS1, CS4, CS8, and CS11, plant protection products had a significant impact on terrestrial, freshwater, and marine ecotoxicity. This is due to their active ingredients, which, depending on the concentration, can harm both the environment and living organisms. These

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active ingredients can inhibit the mobility, growth, and reproduction of vital soil organisms such as microbes, earthworms, and insects—organisms essential for nutrient cycling, decomposition, and maintaining soil structure.

It is important to highlight that shifting agricultural land management toward practices that minimize soil disturbance and increase organic matter, such as reduced tillage, cover crops, and crop rotation, can effectively create a net carbon sink in soils, as demonstrated in case studies CS8, CS9, CS11 and CS14b, and ultimately, enhance essential soil-derived ecosystem services, such as erosion control, biodiversity support, water retention, nutrient cycling, and improved soil fertility.

5. References

- Allen, R. G., Pereira, L. S., & Raes, D. (1998). *FAO Irrigation and drainage paper No. 56*.
- Anikwe, M. A. N., & Ife, K. (2023). The role of soil ecosystem services in the circular bioeconomy. *Frontiers in Soil Science*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsoil.2023.1209100>
- Bauwens, L., & Waeyenberge, L. (2022). *Improving agro-ecological wheat production by application of different sources of green manure*.
- Beaumelle, L., Tison, L., Eisenhauer, N., Hines, J., Malladi, S., Pelosi, C., Thouvenot, L., & Phillips, H. R. P. (2023). Pesticide effects on soil fauna communities—A meta-analysis. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 60(7), 1239–1253. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14437>
- Bind, D. A., van Capelle, C., Tschentke, B., & Schrader, S. (2022). *Soil biodiversity enhancement in European agroecosystems to promote their stability and resilience by external input reduction and crop performance increase*.
- Colomb, V., Ait Amar, S., Mens, C. B., Gac, A., Gaillard, G., Koch, P., Mousset, J., Salou, T., Tailleur, A., & van der Werf, H. M. G. (2015). AGRIBALYSE®, the French LCI Database for agricultural products: high quality data for producers and environmental labelling. *OCL*, 22(1), D104. <https://doi.org/10.1051/ocl/20140047>
- Corsi, S., Friedrich, T., Kassam, A., Pisante, M., & Moraes, J. de. (2012). *Soil Organic Carbon Accumulation and Greenhouse Gas Emission Reductions from Conservation Agriculture: A literature review* (Vol. 16). Plant production and protection division food and agriculture organization of the United Nations.
- De Bruyn, S., Bijleveld, M., de Graaff, L., & Schep, E. (2018). *Environmental Prices Handbook* (CE Delft, Ed. ; EU28 version). CE Delft.
- EMEP/EEA. (2019). *EMEP/EEA air pollutant emission inventory guidebook 2019* (Vol. 13). Office of the European Union.
- Faist Emmenegger, M., Reinhard, J., & Zah, R. (2009). *Sustainability Quick Check for Biofuels – intermediate background report. With contributions from T. Ziep, R. Weichbrodt, Prof. Dr. V. Wohlgemuth, FHTW Berlin and A. Roches, R. Freiermuth Knuchel, Dr. G. Gaillard, Agroscope Reckenholz-Tänikon. Dübendorf, Switzerland*.
- FAO. (2019). *Recarbonization of global soils: A tool to support the implementation of the Koronivia joint work on agriculture*. 12pp. <https://www.fao.org/3/ca6522en/CA6522EN.pdf>
- Fleerackers, S., & Van den Eynde, R. (2022). *Extensification of conventional and organic vegetable farming*.

- Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). (2017). *Unlocking the potential of organic carbon soil. Outcome document of the global symposium on soil organic carbon.*
- González-García, S., Almeida, F., Moreira, M. T., & Brandão, M. (2021). Evaluating the environmental profiles of winter wheat rotation systems under different management strategies. *Science of The Total Environment*, 770, 145270. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.145270>
- Hartmann, M., & Six, J. (2022a). Soil structure and microbiome functions in agroecosystems. *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*, 4(1), 4–18. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-022-00366-w>
- Hartmann, M., & Six, J. (2022b). Soil structure and microbiome functions in agroecosystems. *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*, 4(1), 4–18. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-022-00366-w>
- Huijbregts, M. A. J., Steinmann, Z. J. N., Elshout, P. M. F., Stam, G., Verones, F., Vieira, M., Zijp, M., Hollander, A., & van Zelm, R. (2017). ReCiPe2016: a harmonised life cycle impact assessment method at midpoint and endpoint level. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 22(2), 138–147. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-016-1246-y>
- IPCC. (2006a). *IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories - Agriculture, forestry and other land use.* (Vol. 4).
- IPCC. (2006b). *IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories - Agriculture, forestry and other land use.* (Vol. 4).
- ISO 14040. (2006a). *Environmental management. life cycle assessment. principles and framework.* Bsi.
- ISO 14040. (2006b). *Environmental management. life cycle assessment. principles and framework.* Bsi.
- Kopton, J., Michalke, A., & Schiffers, K. (2023, September 6). Functional Units for Multifunctional Agricultural Systems. *LCM 2023, The 11th International Conference on Life Cycle Management.*
- Masciandaro, G., Macci, C., Peruzzi, E., & Doni, S. (2018). Soil Carbon in the World: Ecosystem Services Linked to Soil Carbon in Forest and Agricultural Soils. In *The Future of Soil Carbon* (pp. 1–38). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-811687-6.00001-8>
- Mtalo, E., Mtalo, E. G., & Derenyi, E. (2019). *A knowledge-based approach to the management of soil erosion information in developing countries.* <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332528282>
- Nemecek, T., Bengoa, X., Lansche, J., Roesch, A., Faist-Emmenegger, M., Rossi, V., Sébastien, H., & Agroscope,). (2019). *World Food LCA Database Methodological Guidelines for the Life Cycle Inventory of Agricultural Products With contributions from Patrik Mouron (1) and Eliane Riedener (1) (up to version 3.0) 2.* www.agroscope.admin.ch

- Ollio, I., Martínez-Martínez, S., Zornoza, R., Egea, C., & Fernández, J. A. (2022). *Use of soil biodiversity to reduce soil-borne diseases/pests incidence and increase nutrient availability in potatoes cropped in multiple cropping and rotations (Spain)*.
- Panagos, P., Borrelli, P., Meusburger, K., Alewell, C., Lugato, E., & Montanarella, L. (2015). Estimating the soil erosion cover-management factor at the European scale. *Land Use Policy*, 48, 38–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2015.05.021>
- Panagos, P., Van Liedekerke, M., Borrelli, P., Köninger, J., Ballabio, C., Orgiazzi, A., Lugato, E., Liakos, L., Hervas, J., Jones, A., & Montanarella, L. (2022). European Soil Data Centre 2.0: Soil data and knowledge in support of the <sc>EU</sc> policies. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 73(6). <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13315>
- Peltoniemi, K., Jooa, J., Mattila, T., Mattila, I., Hagner, M., Pitkänen, J. M., Sarikka, I., Nuutinen, V., Waeyenberge, L., & Calvino, D. F. (2022). *Contrasting minimum tillage and continuous plant cover with inversion tillage in wheat fields in boreal region*.
- Pérez-Rodríguez, P., Fernández-Calviño, D., Álvarez-Pousa, S., & Látr, A. (2022). *Use of mycorrhiza in potato fields to reduce the incidence of common scab, decrease the use of phosphorus fertilizers, increase crop yields and soil biodiversity*.
- Pietrzak, S., Pazikowska-Sapota, G., Dembska, G., Dzierzbicka-Glowacka, L. A., Juskowska, D., Majewska, Z., Urbaniak, M., Ostrowska, D., Cichowska, A., & Galer-Tatarowicz, K. (2020). Risk of phosphorus losses in surface runoff from agricultural land in the Baltic Commune of Puck in the light of assessment performed on the basis of DPS indicator. *PeerJ*, 2020(1). <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.8396>
- Prasuhn, V. (2006). Erfassung der PO₄-Austräge für die Ökobilanzierung - SALCA-Phosphor. *Agroscope FAL Reckenholz*, 22.
- Rojo Serrano, L., Martínez, A., Bravo, R., Sanabria, J. J., & Martín, S. (2022). *MAPA DEL CARBONO ORGÁNICO DEL SUELO EN ESPAÑA* (Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico (MITECO), Ed.). www.miteco.es
- Wernet, G., Bauer, C., Steubing, B., Reinhard, J., Moreno-Ruiz, E., & Weidema, B. (2016). The ecoinvent database version 3 (part I): overview and methodology. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 21(9), 1218–1230. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-016-1087-8>

6. Annex A: Life cycle inventory

Table 10: Case study 1 crop rotation inventory data for each of the different treatments, referring to plot and crop parameters.

CASE STUDY INFO					FAO DATA		YIELD	PLOT PARAMETERS										CROP PARAMETERS			
Case study	Location	Treatment	Year	Crop	FAO ecozones (table 20 WFLDB)	Carbon content (t/3000) FAO	Production (kg)	Repetitions	P (mm)	Total Area (m ²)	Clay (%)	Soil pH	Bulk density (kg/m ³)	Slope factor (LS)	Erodibility factor (K) (ton hr/MJ mm)	Erosivity factor (R) (MJ mm/ha yr)	Practice factor (P)	Tillage factor (c2)	Rooting depth (L) (m)	Nitrogen uptake by crop (U) (kg N/ha)	Crop factor (c1)
1	Cartagena, Murcia	T1: control 100%	2021	Potato	Warm temperate dry	25	4200.49	4	162	735	25.375	9.4	1403	0.319	0.043	473.857	0.96	1	0.5	150	0.34
		T2: control 70%			Warm temperate dry	25	4455.68	4	162	735	25.375	9.4	1403	0.319	0.043	473.857	0.96	1	0.5	150	0.34
		T3: 70% + nuve			Warm temperate dry	25	4343.48	4	162	735	25.375	9.4	1403	0.319	0.043	473.857	0.96	1	0.5	150	0.34
		T4: 70% + bactoneco			Warm temperate dry	25	4090.68	4	162	735	25.375	9.4	1403	0.319	0.043	473.857	0.96	1	0.5	150	0.34
		T1: control 100%	2022	Broccoli	Warm temperate dry	25	332.59	3	146	735	25.375	9.4	1403	0.319	0.043	473.857	0.96	1	0.55	212	0.56
		T2: control 50%			Warm temperate dry	25	309.31	3	146	735	25.375	9.4	1403	0.319	0.043	473.857	0.96	1	0.55	212	0.56
		T3: 50% + nuve			Warm temperate dry	25	298.63	3	146	735	25.375	9.4	1403	0.319	0.043	473.857	0.96	1	0.55	212	0.56
		T4: 50% + bactoneco			Warm temperate dry	25	295.58	3	146	735	25.375	9.4	1403	0.319	0.043	473.857	0.96	1	0.55	212	0.56
		T1: control 100%	2023	Melon	Warm temperate dry	25	2835.11	4	495	735	25.375	9.4	1403	0.319	0.043	473.857	0.96	1	1.15	200	0.45
		T2: control 50%			Warm temperate dry	25	2650.03	4	495	735	25.375	9.4	1403	0.319	0.043	473.857	0.96	1	1.15	200	0.45
		T3: 50% + nuve			Warm temperate dry	25	2809.47	4	495	735	25.375	9.4	1403	0.319	0.043	473.857	0.96	1	1.15	200	0.45
		T4: 50% + bactoneco			Warm temperate dry	25	2874.36	4	495	735	25.375	9.4	1403	0.319	0.043	473.857	0.96	1	1.15	200	0.45

Table 11: Case study 1 crop rotation inventory data for each of the different treatments, referring to inputs.

CASE STUDY INFO					INPUTS (ENERGY. WATER. SEEDS. DIESEL)					INPUT FERTILISERS																
Case study	Location	Treatment	Year	Crop	Irrigation water (m ³)	Diesel (L)	Electricity (kWh)	Type of seeds I	Seeds (kg)	Type of organic fertiliser I	kg	Type of mineral fertiliser I	N (kg)	P ₂ O ₅ (kg)	K ₂ O (kg)	Type of mineral fertiliser II	N (kg)	K ₂ O (kg)	Type of mineral fertiliser III	N (kg)	Type of mineral fertiliser IV	N (kg)	P ₂ O ₅ (kg)			
1	Cartagena. Murcia	T1: control 100%	2021	Potato	155.84	22.906	10.481	Potato	204.16	Sheep manure	110.25	Potassium nitrate (NK)	3.88		12.18											
		T2: control 70%			155.84	22.906	10.481	Potato	204.16	Sheep manure	77.18	Potassium nitrate (NK)	2.73		8.58											
		T3: 70% + nuve			155.99	22.906	10.49	Potato	204.16	Sheep manure	77.18	Potassium nitrate (NK)	2.73		8.58											
		T4: 70% + bactoneco			155.94	22.906	10.487	Potato	204.16	Sheep manure	77.18	Potassium nitrate (NK)	2.73		8.58											
	Cartagena. Murcia	T1: control 100%	2022	Broccoli	26.04	4.002	1.54	Broccoli	1.264				Monoammonium phosphate (MAP)	0.27	1.35		Potassium nitrate (NK)	1.53	4.8	Ammonium nitrate (AN)	1.41	NP fertilizer (Triple pH regulator)	0.00062	0.0023		
		T2: control 50%			26.04	4.002	1.54	Broccoli	1.264					Monoammonium phosphate (MAP)	0.13	0.68		Potassium nitrate (NK)	0.77	2.41	Ammonium nitrate (AN)	0.71	NP fertilizer (Triple pH regulator)	0.00062	0.0023	
		T3: 50% + nuve			26.04	4.002	1.54	Broccoli	1.264					Monoammonium phosphate (MAP)	0.134	0.68		Potassium nitrate (NK)	0.77	2.41	Ammonium nitrate (AN)	0.71	NP fertilizer (Triple pH regulator)	0.00062	0.0023	
		T4: 50% + bactoneco			26.04	4.002	1.54	Broccoli	1.264					Monoammonium phosphate (MAP)	0.134	0.68		Potassium nitrate (NK)	0.77	2.41	Ammonium nitrate (AN)	0.71	NP fertilizer (Triple pH regulator)	0.00062	0.0023	
	Cartagena. Murcia	T1: control 100%	2023	Melon	295.5	46.27	19.93	Melon	296.62				Monoammonium phosphate (MAP)	1.36	6.93		Potassium sulfate		21.5	Ammonium nitrate (AN)	12.42					
		T2: control 50%			295.5	46.27	19.93	Melon	296.62					Monoammonium phosphate (MAP)	0.68	3.47		Potassium sulfate		10.75	Ammonium nitrate (AN)	6.21				
		T3: 50% + nuve			295.5	46.27	19.93	Melon	296.62					Monoammonium phosphate (MAP)	0.688	3.47		Potassium sulfate		10.75	Ammonium nitrate (AN)	6.21				
		T4: 50% + bactoneco			295.5	46.27	19.93	Melon	296.62					Monoammonium phosphate (MAP)	0.68	3.47		Potassium sulfate		10.75	Ammonium nitrate (AN)	6.21				

Table 12: Case study 1 crop rotation inventory data for each of the different treatments, referring to inputs.

CASE STUDY INFO					INPUT PHYTOSANITARY														
Case study	Location	Treatment	Year	Crop	Name of the nutrient I	Nutrients (kg)	Name of the nutrient II	Nutrients (kg)	Name of the nutrient II	Nutrients (kg)	Name of the product II	PPP (kg)	Name of the product III	PPP (kg)	Name of the product IV	PPP (kg)	Name of the product	PPP (kg)	
1	Cartagena. Murcia	T1: control 100%	2021	Potato	Vitalfit	0.1					Carial-Top fungicide	0.0444	Eclipse 70 WG herbicide	0.055					
		T2: control 70%			Vitalfit	0.1				Carial-Top fungicide	0.0444	Eclipse 70 WG herbicide	0.055						
		T3: 70% + nuve			Vitalfit	0.1	Nuve	2.205	Nuve	2.205	Carial-Top fungicide	0.0444	Eclipse 70 WG herbicide	0.055					
		T4: 70% + bactoneco			Vitalfit	0.1	Bactoneco	0.441	Bactoneco	0.441	Carial-Top fungicide	0.0444	Eclipse 70 WG herbicide	0.055					
		T1: control 100%	2022	Broccoli								Karate zeon insecticide	0.02	Ortiva fungicide	0.02				
		T2: control 50%										Karate zeon insecticide	0.02	Ortiva fungicide	0.02				
		T3: 50% + nuve				Nuve	0.6	Nuve	0.6	Karate zeon insecticide	0.02	Ortiva fungicide	0.02						
		T4: 50% + bactoneco				Bactoneco	0.12	Bactoneco	0.12	Karate zeon insecticide	0.02	Ortiva fungicide	0.02						
	T1: control 100%	2023	Melon								Azufega fungicide	2.15	Cal-Ex insecticide	0.125	Trieffect insecticide	0.075	Actum fungicide	0.0625	
	T2: control 50%										Azufega fungicide	2.15	Cal-Ex insecticide	0.125	Trieffect insecticide	0.075	Actum fungicide	0.0625	
	T3: 50% + nuve				Nuve	2.58	Nuve	2.58	Azufega fungicide	2.15	Cal-Ex insecticide	0.125	Trieffect insecticide	0.075	Actum fungicide	0.0625			
	T4: 50% + bactoneco				Bactoneco	0.516	Bactoneco	0.516	Azufega fungicide	2.15	Cal-Ex insecticide	0.125	Trieffect insecticide	0.075	Actum fungicide	0.0625			

Table 13: Case study 4 crop rotation inventory data for each of the different treatments, referring to plot and crop parameters.

CASE STUDY INFO					FAO DATA		YIELD	PLOT PARAMETERS										CROP PARAMETERS			
Case study	Location	Treatment	Year	Crop	FAO ecozones (table 20 WFLDB)	Carbon content (t/3000) FAO	Production (kg)	Repetitions	P (mm)	Total Area (m ²)	Clay (%)	Soil pH	Bulk density (kg/m ³)	Slope factor (LS)	Erodibility factor (K) (ton hr/MJ mm)	Erosivity factor (R) (MJ mm/ha yr)	Practice factor (P)	Tillage factor (c2)	Rooting depth (L) (m)	Nitrogen uptake by crop (U) (kg N/ha)	Crop factor (c1)
4	Sandianes. Ourense. Spain	T1: conventional	2021	Potato	Warm temperate dry	25	3730.34	4	678.6	720	17.85	5.67	1300	0.204	0.026	1011.838	0.875	1	0.5	150	0.34
		T2: No mycorrhizae. 50% P			Warm temperate dry	25	3415.52	4	678.6	720	17.85	5.67	1300	0.204	0.026	1011.838	0.875	1	0.5	150	0.34
		T3: No mycorrhizae. no P			Warm temperate dry	25	3954.96	4	678.6	720	17.85	5.67	1300	0.204	0.026	1011.838	0.875	1	0.5	150	0.34
		T4: mycorrhizae. 50% P			Warm temperate dry	25	4583.43	4	678.6	720	17.85	5.67	1300	0.204	0.026	1011.838	0.875	1	0.5	150	0.34
		T5: mycorrhizae. no P			Warm temperate dry	25	4378.07	4	678.6	720	17.85	5.67	1300	0.204	0.026	1011.838	0.875	1	0.5	150	0.34
		T1	2022	Barley	Warm temperate dry	25	3125	1	780	10000	17.85	5.67	1300	0.204	0.026	1011.838	0.875	1	1.25	210	0.21
		T1: conventional			Warm temperate dry	25	3245.61	4	780	720	17.85	5.67	1300	0.204	0.026	1011.838	0.875	1	0.5	150	0.34
		T2: No mycorrhizae. 50% P			Warm temperate dry	25	2720.67	4	780	720	17.85	5.67	1300	0.204	0.026	1011.838	0.875	1	0.5	150	0.34
		T3: No mycorrhizae. no P			Warm temperate dry	25	3050.73	4	780	720	17.85	5.67	1300	0.204	0.026	1011.838	0.875	1	0.5	150	0.34
		T4: mycorrhizae. 50% P			Warm temperate dry	25	2615.35	4	780	720	17.85	5.67	1300	0.204	0.026	1011.838	0.875	1	0.5	150	0.34
T5: mycorrhizae. no P	Warm temperate dry	25	2973.17	4	780	720	17.85	5.67	1300	0.204	0.026	1011.838	0.875	1	0.5	150	0.34				

Table 14: Case study 4 crop rotation inventory data for each of the different treatments, referring to crop parameters and inputs.

CASE STUDY INFO					INPUTS (ENERGY. WATER. SEEDS. DIESEL)					INPUT FERTILISERS												
Case study	Location	Treatment	Year	Crop	Irrigation water (m ³)	Diesel (L)	Electricity (kWh)	Type of seeds I	Seeds (kg)	Type of mineral fertiliser I	N (kg)	P ₂ O ₅ (kg)	K ₂ O (kg)	Type of mineral fertiliser II	K ₂ O (kg)	Type of mineral fertiliser III	N (kg)	P ₂ O ₅ (kg)	Type of mineral fertiliser IV	N (kg)		
4	Sandianes. Ourense. Spain	T1: conventional	2021	Potato	60	19.94	40	Potato	252	Ammonium sulphate (AS)	8.40			Potassium sulfate	25.00	Superphosphate		32.4	CAN 27%	6.75		
		T2: No mycorrhizae. 50% P			60	19.94	40	Potato	252	Ammonium sulphate (AS)	8.40			Potassium sulfate	25.00	Superphosphate		16.2	CAN 27%	6.75		
		T3: No mycorrhizae. no P			60	19.89	40	Potato	252	Ammonium sulphate (AS)	8.40			Potassium sulfate	25.00	CAN 27%	6.75					
		T4: mycorrhizae. 50% P			60	19.8	40	Potato	252	Ammonium sulphate (AS)	8.40			Potassium sulfate	25.00	Superphosphate		16.2	CAN 27%	6.75		
		T5: mycorrhizae. no P			60	19.89	40	Potato	252	Ammonium sulphate (AS)	8.40			Potassium sulfate	25.00	CAN 27%	6.75					
		T1	2022	Barley	81.73			Barley	200	NPK	21.00	30	21									
		T1: conventional			78	18.18	52	Potato	180	Urea ammonium nitrate (UAN)	9.20			Potassium sulfate	25.00	Superphosphate		10.08	CAN 27%	6.75		
		T2: No mycorrhizae. 50% P			78	18.18	52	Potato	180	Urea ammonium nitrate (UAN)	9.20			Potassium sulfate	25.00	Superphosphate		5.04	CAN 27%	6.75		
		T3: No mycorrhizae. no P			78	18.74	52	Potato	180	Urea ammonium nitrate (UAN)	9.20			Potassium sulfate	25.00	CAN 27%	6.75					
		T4: mycorrhizae. 50% P			78	18.18	52	Potato	180	Urea ammonium nitrate (UAN)	9.20			Potassium sulfate	25.00	Superphosphate		5.04	CAN 27%	6.75		
		T5: mycorrhizae. no P			78	18.74	52	Potato	180	Urea ammonium nitrate (UAN)	9.20			Potassium sulfate	25.00	CAN 27%	6.75					

Table 15: Case study 4 crop rotation inventory data for each of the different treatments, referring to inputs.

CASE STUDY INFO					INPUT PHYTOSANITARY																			
Case study	Location	Treatment	Year	Crop	Name of the nutrient I	Nutrients (kg)	Name of the product II	PPP (kg)	Name of the product III	PPP (kg)	Name of the product IV	PPP (kg)	Name of the product V	PPP (kg)	Name of the product VI	PPP (kg)	Name of the product VII	PPP (kg)	Name of the product VIII	PPP (kg)	Name of the product IX	PPP (kg)		
4	Sandianes. Ourense. Spain	T1: conventional	2021	Potato			Metric herbicide	0.163	Volare fungicide	0.49	Epik insecticide	0.022	Kabuto fungicide	0.077	Sumifive insecticide	0.027	Milraz pro fungicide	0.045	Gonzai herbicide	0.093				
		T2: No mycorrhizae. 50% P				Metric herbicide	0.163	Volare fungicide	0.49	Epik insecticide	0.022	Kabuto fungicide	0.077	Sumifive insecticide	0.027	Milraz pro fungicide	0.045	Gonzai herbicide	0.093					
		T3: No mycorrhizae. no P				Metric herbicide	0.1623	Volare fungicide	0.49	Epik insecticide	0.022	Kabuto fungicide	0.077	Sumifive insecticide	0.027	Milraz pro fungicide	0.045	Gonzai herbicide	0.093					
		T4: mycorrhizae. 50% P			Mycorrhizae	1.8	Metric herbicide	0.163	Volare fungicide	0.49	Epik insecticide	0.022	Kabuto fungicide	0.077	Sumifive insecticide	0.027	Milraz pro fungicide	0.045	Gonzai herbicide	0.093				
		T5: mycorrhizae. no P			Mycorrhizae	1.8	Metric herbicide	0.163	Volare fungicide	0.49	Epik insecticide	0.022	Kabuto fungicide	0.077	Sumifive insecticide	0.027	Milraz pro fungicide	0.045	Gonzai herbicide	0.093				
		T1	2022	Barley				Posta herbicide	0.05															
		T1: conventional				Bismark herbicide	0.121	Volare fungicide	0.31	Xanilo fungicide	0.054	Revus fungicide	0.072	Lieto fungicide	0.032	Milraz pro fungicide	0.032	Epik insecticide	0.018	Leimay fungicide	0.037			
		T2: No mycorrhizae. 50% P				Bismark herbicide	0.121	Volare fungicide	0.31	Xanilo fungicide	0.054	Revus fungicide	0.072	Lieto fungicide	0.032	Milraz pro fungicide	0.032	Epik insecticide	0.018	Leimay fungicide	0.037			
		T3: No mycorrhizae. no P				Bismark herbicide	0.121	Volare fungicide	0.31	Xanilo fungicide	0.054	Revus fungicide	0.072	Lieto fungicide	0.032	Milraz pro fungicide	0.032	Epik insecticide	0.018	Leimay fungicide	0.037			
		T4: mycorrhizae. 50% P			Mycorrhizae	1.8	Bismark herbicide	0.121	Volare fungicide	0.31	Xanilo fungicide	0.054	Revus fungicide	0.072	Lieto fungicide	0.032	Milraz pro fungicide	0.032	Epik insecticide	0.018	Leimay fungicide	0.037		
T5: mycorrhizae. no P	Mycorrhizae	1.8	Bismark herbicide	0.121	Volare fungicide	0.31	Xanilo fungicide	0.054	Revus fungicide	0.072	Lieto fungicide	0.032	Milraz pro fungicide	0.032	Epik insecticide	0.018	Leimay fungicide	0.037						

Table 16: Case study 8 crop rotation inventory data for each of the different treatments, referring to plot and crop parameters.

CASE STUDY INFO					FAO DATA		YIELD	PLOT PARAMETERS										CROP PARAMETERS			
Case study	Location	Treatment	Year	Crop	FAO ecozones (table 20 WFLDB)	Carbon content (t/3000) FAO	Production (kg)	Repetitions	P (mm)	Total Area (m ²)	Clay (%)	Soil pH	Bulk density (kg/m ³)	Slope factor (LS)	Erodibility factor (K) (ton hr/MJ mm)	Erosivity factor (R) (MJ mm/ha yr)	Practice factor (P)	Tillage factor (c2)	Rooting depth (L) (m)	Nitrogen uptake by crop (U) (kg N/ha)	Crop factor (c1)
8	Sint-Katelijne-Waver, Belgium	T1: Conventional. Intensive	2021	Leek	Cool temperate moist	81	2820.66	4	729.93	530	7.756	7.13	1281	0.136	0.038	631.981	0.925	1	0.3	130	0.35
		T2: Conventional. Extensive			Cool temperate moist	81	2764.12	4	729.93	530	7.756	7.13	1281	0.136	0.038	631.981	0.925	0.35	0.3	130	0.35
		T3: Organic. intensive			Cool temperate moist	81	1399.66	4	729.93	480	7.756	7.13	1281	0.136	0.038	631.981	0.925	1	0.3	130	0.35
		T4: Organic. extensive			Cool temperate moist	81	1526.33	4	729.93	470	7.756	7.13	1281	0.136	0.038	631.981	0.925	0.35	0.3	130	0.35
		T1: Conventional. Intensive	2022	Celery	Cool temperate moist	81	1662	4	729.93	530	7.756	7.13	1281	0.136	0.038	631.981	0.925	1	0.4	311.1	0.7
		T2: Conventional. Extensive			Cool temperate moist	81	1450	4	729.93	530	7.756	7.13	1281	0.136	0.038	631.981	0.925	0.35	0.4	311.2	0.7
		T3: Organic. intensive			Cool temperate moist	81	857.28	4	729.93	480	7.756	7.13	1281	0.136	0.038	631.981	0.925	1	0.4	311.3	0.7
		T4: Organic. extensive			Cool temperate moist	81	1044.81	4	729.93	470	7.756	7.13	1281	0.136	0.038	631.981	0.925	0.35	0.4	311.4	0.7
	T1: Conventional. Intensive	2023	Cauliflower	Cool temperate moist	81	3118	4	729.93	530	7.756	7.13	1281	0.136	0.038	631.981	0.925	1	0.55	151	0.7	
	T2: Conventional. Extensive			Cool temperate moist	81	3120	4	729.93	530	7.756	7.13	1281	0.136	0.038	631.981	0.925	0.35	0.55	151	0.7	
	T3: Organic. intensive			Cool temperate moist	81	3069	4	729.93	480	7.756	7.13	1281	0.136	0.038	631.981	0.925	1	0.55	151	0.7	
	T4: Organic. extensive			Cool temperate moist	81	3101	4	729.93	470	7.756	7.13	1281	0.136	0.038	631.981	0.925	0.35	0.55	151	0.7	

Table 17: Case study 14b crop rotation inventory data for each of the different treatments, referring to inputs.

CASE STUDY INFO					INPUTS (ENERGY. WATER. SEEDS. DIESEL)									INPUT FERTILISERS												
Case study	Location	Treatment	Year	Crop	Diesel (L)	Type of seeds I	Seeds (kg)	Type of seeds II	Seeds (kg)	Type of seeds III	Seeds (kg)	Type of seeds III	Seeds (kg)	Type of organic fertiliser I	Organic fertiliser (kg)	Type of organic fertiliser II	Organic fertiliser (kg)	Type of mineral fertiliser I	N (kg)	K ₂ O (kg)	Type of mineral fertiliser II	N (kg)	P ₂ O ₅ (kg)			
8	Sint-Katelijne-Waver, Belgium	T1: Conventional. Intensive	2021	Leek	57.62	Leek	416.34												Potassium chloride 60		6.3	Di ammonium phosphate (DAP)	0.40	1.36		
		T2: Conventional. Extensive			52.89	Leek	416.34							Green waste compost	890				Potassium chloride 60		6.3					
		T3: Organic. intensive			49.97	Leek	375.22							Cattle slurry	1680											
		T4: Organic. extensive			46.97	Leek	375.22							Farmyard manure (cattle)	1080											
		T1: Conventional. Intensive	2022	Celery	70	Celery	128.69													Calcium ammonium nitrate (CAN)	4.72					
		T2: Conventional. Extensive			64.25	Celery	128.69	<i>Phacelia sp.</i>	0.27	Crimson clover	1.1	Italian ryegrass	2.12	Green waste compost	2100					Calcium ammonium nitrate (CAN)	6.30					
		T3: Organic. intensive			57.97	Celery	114.13	<i>Phacelia sp.</i>	0.24	Crimson clover	0.94	Italian ryegrass	2.12	Green waste compost	1890	NK (11-3) organic fertilizer	39.84									
		T4: Organic. extensive			57.97	Celery	114.13	<i>Phacelia sp.</i>	0.24	Crimson clover	0.94	Italian ryegrass	2.12	Green waste compost	1890	NK (11-3) organic fertilizer	39.09									
	T1: Conventional. Intensive	2023	Cauliflower	40.3	Cauliflower	3150													Urea	43.5						
	T2: Conventional. Extensive			44.43	Cauliflower	3150	<i>Phacelia sp.</i>	0.42					Green waste compost	2100					Urea	39.12						
	T3: Organic. intensive			93.73	Cauliflower	2700							Farmyard manure (cattle)	2961	Biomix 2 extra (N 12%)	70.08										
	T4: Organic. extensive			90.54	Cauliflower	2700	<i>Phacelia sp.</i>	0.42					Green waste compost	1890	Biomix 2 extra (N 12%)	63.6										

Table 18: Case study 8 crop rotation inventory data for each of the different treatments, referring to inputs.

CASE STUDY INFO					INPUT PHYTOSANITARY													
Case study	Location	Treatment	Year	Crop	Name of the nutrient I	Nutrients (kg)	Name of the nutrient II	Nutrients (kg)	Name of the product II	PPP (kg)	Name of the product III	PPP (kg)	Name of the product IV	PPP (kg)	Name of the product	PPP (kg)		
8	Sint-Katelijne-Waver, Belgium	T1: Conventional. Intensive	2021	Leek	Biosweet	0.40			Stomp Aqua herbicide	0.093	Xinca herbicide	0.033	Lentagran 45 WP herbicide	0.024	Benevia insecticide	0.046		
		T2: Conventional. Extensive			Biosweet	0.40			Stomp Aqua herbicide	0.093	Xinca herbicide	0.033	Lentagran 45 WP herbicide	0.024	Benevia insecticide	0.046		
		T3: Organic. intensive																
		T4: Organic. extensive																
			T1: Conventional. Intensive	2022	Celery					Metarex Inov insecticide	0.26	Centium herbicide	0.013	Defi herbicide	0.32	Challenge herbicide	0.032	
			T2: Conventional. Extensive							Metarex Inov insecticide	0.26	Centium herbicide	0.013	Defi herbicide	0.32	Challenge herbicide	0.032	
			T3: Organic. intensive															
			T4: Organic. extensive															
		T1: Conventional. Intensive	2023	Cauliflower	Mantrac 500	0.083	Lime	276	Glyfall Plus herbicide	0.32	Conserve pro insecticide	0.07	Infinito fungicide	0.17	Limatex insecticide	0.26		
		T2: Conventional. Extensive							Lime	276	Glyfall Plus herbicide	0.32	Conserve pro insecticide	0.07	Infinito fungicide	0.17	Limatex insecticide	0.26
		T3: Organic. intensive								Lime	276	Conserve pro insecticide	0.07	Sluux insecticide	0.34			
		T4: Organic. extensive								Lime	276	Conserve pro insecticide	0.06	Sluux insecticide	0.33			

Table 19: Case study 8 crop rotation inventory data for each of the different treatments, referring to inputs.

CASE STUDY INFO					INPUT PHYTOSANITARY																	
Case study	Location	Treatment	Year	Crop	Name of the product V	PPP (kg)	Name of the product VI	PPP (kg)	Name of the product VII	PPP (kg)	Name of the product VIII	PPP (kg)	Name of the product IX	PPP (kg)	Name of the product X	PPP (kg)	Name of the product XI	PPP (kg)	Name of the product XII	PPP (kg)		
8	Sint-Katelijne-Waver, Belgium	T1: Conventional, Intensive	2021	Leek	Conserve pro insecticide	0,126	Vertimec insecticide	0,057	Tebusip fungicide	0,13												
		T2: Conventional, Extensive			Conserve pro insecticide	0,126	Vertimec insecticide	0,057	Tebusip fungicide	0,13												
		T3: Organic, intensive																				
		T4: Organic, extensive																				
			T1: Conventional, Intensive	2022	Celery	Ortiva Top fungicide	0,058	Conserve pro insecticide	0,042	Nativo 75 fungicide	0,042	Ultror insecticide	0,026	Trend 90 wetting agent	0,024							
	T2: Conventional, Extensive	Ortiva Top fungicide	0,058			Conserve pro insecticide	0,042	Nativo 75 fungicide	0,042	Ultror insecticide	0,026	Trend 90 wetting agent	0,024									
	T3: Organic, intensive																					
	T4: Organic, extensive																					
		T1: Conventional, Intensive	2023	Cauliflower	Rapsan 500 herbicide	0,09	Frontier herbicide	0,066	Verimark insecticide	0,023	Sluxx insecticide	0,11	Benevia insecticide	0,040	Actirob B herbicide	0,024	Ultror insecticide	0,027	Ortiva Top fungicide	0,061		
T2: Conventional, Extensive	Rapsan 500 herbicide	0,12			Frontier herbicide	0,066	Verimark insecticide	0,023	Sluxx insecticide	0,11	Benevia insecticide	0,040	Actirob B herbicide	0,024	Ultror insecticide	0,027	Ortiva Top fungicide	0,061				
T3: Organic, intensive																						
T4: Organic, extensive																						

Table 20: Case study 9 crop rotation inventory data for each of the different treatments, referring to plot parameters.

CASE STUDY INFO					FAO DATA		YIELD	PLOT PARAMETERS										
Case study	Location	Treatment	Year	Crop	FAO ecozones (table 20 WFLDB)	Carbon content (t/3000) FAO	Production (kg)	Repetitions	P (mm)	Total Area (m ²)	Clay (%)	Soil pH	Bulk density (kg/m ³)	Slope factor (LS)	Erodibility factor (K) (ton hr/MJ mm)	Erosivity factor (R) (MJ mm/ha yr)	Practice factor (P)	Tillage factor (c2)
9	Beveren, Belgium	T1	2020	Wheat	Cool temperate moist	81	2000	4	890.2	4800	14.92	8.28	1535	0.063	0.036	622.324	0.875	0.35
		T1: Cattle manure			Cool temperate moist	81	739	4	890.2	1200	14.92	8.28	1535	0.063	0.036	622.324	0.875	0.35
		T2: Worm compost	2021	Wheat	Cool temperate moist	81	605	4	890.2	1200	14.92	8.28	1535	0.063	0.036	622.324	0.875	0.35
		T3: Grass sillage			Cool temperate moist	81	773	4	890.2	1200	14.92	8.28	1535	0.063	0.036	622.324	0.875	0.35
		T4: Control	2022	Potato	Cool temperate moist	81	638	4	890.2	1200	14.92	8.28	1535	0.063	0.036	622.324	0.875	0.35
		T1: Cattle manure			Cool temperate moist	81	4050	4	890.2	1200	14.92	8.28	1535	0.063	0.036	622.324	0.875	0.35
		T2: Worm compost			Cool temperate moist	81	4500	4	890.2	1200	14.92	8.28	1535	0.063	0.036	622.324	0.875	0.35
		T3: Grass sillage			Cool temperate moist	81	4500	4	890.2	1200	14.92	8.28	1535	0.063	0.036	622.324	0.875	0.35
		T4: Control	Cool temperate moist	81	4050	4	890.2	1200	14.92	8.28	1535	0.063	0.036	622.324	0.875	0.35		

Table 21: Case study 9 crop rotation inventory data for each of the different treatments, referring to crop parameters and inputs.

CASE STUDY INFO					CROP PARAMETERS			INPUTS (ENERGY, WATER, SEEDS, DIESEL)					INPUT FERTILISERS	
Case study	Location	Treatment	Year	Crop	Rooting depth (L) (m)	Nitrogen uptake by crop (U) (kg N/ha)	Crop factor (c1)	Diesel (L)	Type of seeds I	Seeds (kg)	Type of seeds II	Seeds (kg)	Type of organic fertiliser I	Organic fertiliser (kg)
9	Beveren, Belgium	T1	2020	Wheat	1.25	254	0.2	25.36	Wheat	87.5				
		T1: Cattle manure			1.25	254	0.2	14.84	Wheat	46.25	<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	2	Cattle manure	2400
		T2: Worm compost	2021	Wheat	1.25	254	0.2	20.09	Wheat	46.25	<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	2	Worm compost	6840
		T3: Grass silage			1.25	254	0.2	41.1	Wheat	46.25	<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	2	Grass silage	1680
		T4: Control			1.25	254	0.2	14.1	Wheat	46.25	<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	2		
		T1: Cattle manure			0.5	150	0.34	50.05	Potato	75	<i>Phacelia sp.</i>	1.25	Cattle manure	2000
		T2: Worm compost	2022	Potato	0.5	150	0.34	59.23	Potato	75	<i>Phacelia sp.</i>	1.25	Worm compost	2000
		T3: Grass silage			0.5	150	0.34	118.73	Potato	75	<i>Phacelia sp.</i>	1.25	Grass silage	1200
		T4: Control			0.5	150	0.34	48.73	Potato	75	<i>Phacelia sp.</i>	1.25		

Table 22: Case study 11 crop rotation inventory data for each of the different treatments, referring to plot and crop parameters.

CASE STUDY INFO					FAO DATA		YIELD	PLOT PARAMETERS										CROP PARAMETERS			
Case study	Location	Treatment	Year	Crop	FAO ecozones (table 20 WFLDB)	Carbon content (t/3000) FAO	Production (kg)	Repetitions	P (mm)	Total Area (m ²)	Clay (%)	Soil pH	Bulk density (kg/m ³)	Slope factor (LS)	Erodibility factor (K) (ton hr/MJ mm)	Erosivity factor (R) (MJ mm/ha yr)	Practice factor (P)	Tillage factor (c2)	Rooting depth (L) (m)	Nitrogen uptake by crop (U) (kg N/ha)	Crop factor (c1)
11	Nideggen, Germany	T1: Control	2021	Wheat	Cool temperate moist	81	1066	4	600	1440	20.04	6.85	1734	1.867	0.05	597.24	0.98	0.35	1.25	254	0.2
		T2: Extensive			Cool temperate moist	81	774	4	600	1440	20.04	6.85	1734	1.867	0.05	597.24	0.98	0.35	1.25	254	0.2
		T3: Diversified extensive			Cool temperate moist	81	911	4	600	1440	20.04	6.85	1734	1.867	0.05	597.24	0.98	0.35	1.25	254	0.2
		T1: Control	2022	Maize	Cool temperate moist	81	4918	4	600	1440	20.04	6.85	1734	1.867	0.05	597.24	0.98	0.35	1.52	250	0.38
		T2: Extensive			Cool temperate moist	81	4361	4	600	1440	20.04	6.85	1734	1.867	0.05	597.24	0.98	0.35	1.52	250	0.38
		T3: Diversified extensive			Cool temperate moist	81	5321	4	600	1440	20.04	6.85	1734	1.867	0.05	597.24	0.98	0.35	1.52	250	0.38
		T1: Control	2023	Wheat	Cool temperate moist	81	1397	4	600	1440	20.04	6.85	1734	1.867	0.05	597.24	0.98	0.35	1.25	254	0.2
		T2: Extensive			Cool temperate moist	81	1382	4	600	1440	20.04	6.85	1734	1.867	0.05	597.24	0.98	0.35	1.25	254	0.2
		T3: Diversified extensive			Cool temperate moist	81	1505	4	600	1440	20.04	6.85	1734	1.867	0.05	597.24	0.98	0.35	1.25	254	0.2

Table 23: Case study 11 crop rotation inventory data for each of the different treatments, referring to inputs.

CASE STUDY INFO					INPUTS (ENERGY. WATER. SEEDS. DIESEL)					INPUT FERTILISERS											
Case study	Location	Treatment	Year	Crop	Diesel (L)	Type of seeds I	Seeds (kg)	Type of seeds II	Seeds (kg)	Type of mineral fertiliser I	N (kg)	P ₂ O ₅ (kg)	K ₂ O (kg)	Type of mineral fertiliser II	N (kg)	P ₂ O ₅ (kg)	K ₂ O (kg)	Type of mineral fertiliser III	N (kg)		
11	Nideggen, Germany	T1: Control	2021	Wheat	25	Wheat	20.31			Ammonium sulphate	24.88			Urea ammonium nitrate	1.56						
		T2: Extensive			19.43	Wheat	20.31			Ammonium sulphate	24.88			Urea ammonium nitrate	1.56						
		T3: Diversified extensive			28.56	Wheat	20.31	Clover	3.97	Ammonium sulphate	24.88			Urea ammonium nitrate	1.56						
		T1: Control	2022	Maize	27.35	Maize	3.82			Di ammonium phosphate (DAP)	5.18	13.248			NPK	0.004	0.085	0.034	CAN 27%	17.50	
		T2: Extensive			27.35	Maize	3.82			Di ammonium phosphate (DAP)	5.18	13.248			NPK	0.004	0.085	0.034	CAN 27%	17.50	
		T3: Diversified extensive			27.35	Maize	3.82			Di ammonium phosphate (DAP)	5.18	13.248			NPK	0.004	0.085	0.034	CAN 27%	17.50	
		T1: Control	2023	Wheat	38.86	Wheat	26			Ammonium sulphate	11.40				Urea ammonium nitrate	1.56				CAN 27%	11.66
		T2: Extensive			38.86	Wheat	26			Ammonium sulphate	11.40			Urea ammonium nitrate	1.56				CAN 27%	11.66	
		T3: Diversified extensive			38.86	Wheat	26			Ammonium sulphate	11.40			Urea ammonium nitrate	1.56				CAN 27%	11.66	

Table 24: Case study 11 crop rotation inventory data for each of the different treatments, referring to inputs.

CASE STUDY INFO					INPUT PHYTOSANITARY												
Case study	Location	Treatment	Year	Crop	Name of the nutrient I	Nutrients (kg)	Name of the nutrient II	Nutrients (kg)	Name of the product II	PPP (kg)	Name of the product III	PPP (kg)	Name of the product IV	PPP (kg)	Name of the product	PPP (kg)	
11	Nideggen, Germany	T1: Control	2021	Wheat					Durano herbicide	0.42	Boxer herbicide	0.29	Herold herbicide	0.089	Input classic fungicide	0.13	
		T2: Extensive							Durano herbicide	0.42							
		T3: Diversified extensive								Durano herbicide	0.42						
		T1: Control	2022	Maize	Sulfur	14.4	Silica	12.96	Aspect herbicide	0.22	Maister herbicide	0.22					
		T2: Extensive			Sulfur	14.5	Silica	12.96	Aspect herbicide	0.22	Maister herbicide	0.22					
		T3: Diversified extensive			Sulfur	14.4	Silica	12.96	Aspect herbicide	0.22	Maister herbicide	0.22					
		T1: Control	2023	Wheat	CCC720	0.11	Silica	0.020	Boxer herbicide	0.15	Metil herbicide	0.13	Moddus	0.023	Pointer plus herbicide	0.0058	
		T2: Extensive			CCC720	0.11	Silica	0.020	Boxer herbicide	0.15	Metil herbicide	0.13	Moddus	0.023	Pointer plus herbicide	0.0058	
		T3: Diversified extensive			CCC720	0.11	Silica	0.020	Boxer herbicide	0.15	Metil herbicide	0.13	Moddus	0.023	Pointer plus herbicide	0.0058	

Table 25: Case study 11 crop rotation inventory data for each of the different treatments, referring to inputs.

CASE STUDY INFO					INPUT PHYTOSANITARY														
Case study	Location	Treatment	Year	Crop	Name of the product V	PPP (kg)	Name of the product VI	PPP (kg)	Name of the product VII	PPP (kg)	Name of the product VIII	PPP (kg)	Name of the product IX	PPP (kg)	Name of the product X	PPP (kg)	Name of the product XI	PPP (kg)	
11	Nideggen, Germany	T1: Control	2021	Wheat	Prodax fungicide	0.072	Comet fungicide	0.067	Revytrex fungicide	0.20	Fezan fungicide	0.13	Aznany fungicide	0.08	Karate Zeon insecticide	0.011	Pointer plus herbicide	0.0072	
		T2: Extensive																	
		T3: Diversified extensive																	
		T1: Control	2022	Maize	Input classic fungicide	0.14	Axial 50 herbicide	0.17	Balaya fungicide	0.13	Caramba fungicide	0.060	Curbatur fungicide	0.12	Karate zeon insecticide	0.011			
		T2: Extensive																	
		T3: Diversified extensive																	
		T1: Control	2023	Wheat	Input classic fungicide	0.14	Axial 50 herbicide	0.17	Balaya fungicide	0.13	Caramba fungicide	0.060	Curbatur fungicide	0.12	Karate zeon insecticide	0.011			
		T2: Extensive																	
		T3: Diversified extensive																	

Table 26: Case study 14b crop rotation inventory data for each of the different treatments, referring to plot parameters.

CASE STUDY INFO					FAO DATA		YIELD	PLOT PARAMETERS										
Case study	Location	Treatment	Year	Crop	FAO ecozones (table 20 WFLDB)	Carbon content (t/3000) FAO	Production (kg)	Repetitions	P (mm)	Total Area (m ²)	Clay (%)	Soil pH	Bulk density (kg/m ³)	Slope factor (LS)	Erodibility factor (K) (ton hr/MJ mm)	Erosivity factor (R) (MJ mm/ha yr)	Practice factor (P)	Tillage factor (c2)
14b	South Karelia, Finland	T1 (control)	2021	Wheat	Boreal moist	22	2534.6	4	650	5750	31.64	6.62	1200	1.154	0.026	334.659	0.98	1
		T2 (reduce tillage)			Boreal moist	22	1627.54	4	650	5750	31.64	6.62	1200	1.154	0.026	334.659	0.98	0.35
		T1 (control)	2022	Peas	Boreal moist	22	1886.43	4	650	5750	31.64	6.62	1200	1.154	0.026	334.659	0.98	1
		T2 (reduce tillage)			Boreal moist	22	1653.84	4	650	5750	31.64	6.62	1200	1.154	0.026	334.659	0.98	0.35
		T1 (control)	2023	Wheat	Boreal moist	22	1402	4	650	5750	31.64	6.62	1200	1.154	0.026	334.659	0.98	1
		T2 (reduce tillage)			Boreal moist	22	1894	4	650	5750	31.64	6.62	1200	1.154	0.026	334.659	0.98	0.35

Table 27: Case study 14b crop rotation inventory data for each of the different treatments, referring to crop parameters and inputs.

CASE STUDY INFO					CROP PARAMETERS			INPUTS (ENERGY. WATER. SEEDS. DIESEL)							INPUT FERTILISERS	
Case study	Location	Treatment	Year	Crop	Rooting depth (L) (m)	Nitrogen uptake by crop (U) (kg N/ha)	Crop factor (c1)	Diese I (L)	Type of seeds I	Seeds (kg)	Type of seeds II	Seeds (kg)	Type of seeds III	Seeds (kg)	Type of organic fertiliser I	Organic fertiliser (kg)
14b	South Karelia, Finland	T1 (control)	2021	Wheat	1.25	254	0.2	27.04	Wheat	143.75	Cover crop	2.88			Biogas digestate	218.94
		T2 (reduce tillage)			1.25	254	0.2	13.09	Wheat	143.75	Cover crop	2.88			Biogas digestate	218.94
		T1 (control)	2022	Peas	1.25	254	0.5	17.61	Wheat	40.25	Peas	172.5	Ryegrass	4.6		
		T2 (reduce tillage)			1.25	254	0.5	18	Wheat	40.25	Peas	172.5	Ryegrass	4.6		
		T1 (control)	2023	Wheat	1.25	254	0.2	25.63	Wheat	172.5	Cover crop	14.38			Biogas digestate	248.13
		T2 (reduce tillage)			1.25	254	0.2	11.64	Wheat	172.5	Cover crop	14.38			Biogas digestate	248.13

7. Annex B: Environmental impacts results

Table 28: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 1 of the first year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit.

Impact Category	Units	CS1-Y1-T1	CS1-Y1-T2	CS1-Y1-T3	CS1-Y1-T4
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	1.44E-01	1.19E-01	1.22E-01	1.31E-01
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	1.85E-06	1.40E-06	1.46E-06	1.58E-06
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	1.71E-03	1.26E-03	1.31E-03	1.42E-03
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	4.89E-05	4.45E-05	4.61E-05	5.01E-05
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	1.07E-03	9.62E-04	9.98E-04	1.08E-03
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2.83E-01	2.59E-01	2.88E-01	2.96E-01
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2.50E-03	2.30E-03	2.38E-03	2.59E-03
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2.70E-03	2.48E-03	2.58E-03	2.80E-03
Land use	m ² a crop eq	5.39E-01	4.94E-01	5.13E-01	5.57E-01
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	9.91E-03	6.55E-03	6.81E-03	7.39E-03
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	2.46E-02	2.06E-02	2.22E-02	2.34E-02
Water consumption	m ³	1.71E-02	1.56E-02	1.62E-02	1.76E-02

Table 29: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 1 of the first year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha.

Impact Category	Units	CS1-Y1-T1	CS1-Y1-T2	CS1-Y1-T3	CS1-Y1-T4
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	2.82E+03	2.53E+03	2.50E+03	2.47E+03
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	3.61E-02	2.98E-02	2.99E-02	2.99E-02
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	3.33E+01	2.67E+01	2.70E+01	2.68E+01
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	9.54E-01	9.46E-01	9.46E-01	9.46E-01
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	2.08E+01	2.05E+01	2.05E+01	2.05E+01
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	5.52E+03	5.51E+03	5.91E+03	5.59E+03
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	4.88E+01	4.88E+01	4.89E+01	4.89E+01
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	5.28E+01	5.28E+01	5.30E+01	5.28E+01
Land use	m ² a crop eq	1.05E+04	1.05E+04	1.05E+04	1.05E+04
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	1.94E+02	1.39E+02	1.40E+02	1.39E+02
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	4.81E+02	4.38E+02	4.55E+02	4.42E+02
Water consumption	m ³	3.33E+02	3.31E+02	3.32E+02	3.32E+02

Table 30: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 1 of the second year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit.

Impact Category	Units	CS1-Y2-T1	CS1-Y2-T2	CS1-Y2-T3	CS1-Y2-T4
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	4.17E-01	3.31E-01	4.10E-01	3.79E-01
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	5.41E-06	4.01E-06	4.57E-06	4.74E-06

Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	3.05E-03	1.96E-03	2.26E-03	2.32E-03
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	4.15E-04	4.09E-04	4.66E-04	4.84E-04
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	5.83E-03	5.77E-03	6.58E-03	6.82E-03
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	3.20E-01	3.16E-01	3.97E-01	3.81E-01
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	8.74E-04	8.69E-04	9.94E-04	1.03E-03
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	4.38E-03	4.36E-03	4.98E-03	5.15E-03
Land use	m ² a crop eq	3.05E+00	3.03E+00	3.45E+00	3.58E+00
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	2.40E-02	1.30E-02	1.49E-02	1.54E-02
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	5.69E-02	4.26E-02	5.00E-02	5.06E-02
Water consumption	m ³	2.38E-02	2.30E-02	2.63E-02	2.72E-02

Table 31: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 1 of the second year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha.

Impact Category	Units	CS1-Y2-T1	CS1-Y2-T2	CS1-Y2-T3	CS1-Y2-T4
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	1.38E+03	1.10E+03	1.19E+03	1.06E+03
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	1.79E-02	1.33E-02	1.33E-02	1.33E-02
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	1.01E+01	6.51E+00	6.57E+00	6.52E+00
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	1.37E+00	1.36E+00	1.36E+00	1.36E+00
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	1.92E+01	1.92E+01	1.92E+01	1.92E+01
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.06E+03	1.05E+03	1.16E+03	1.07E+03
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2.88E+00	2.88E+00	2.90E+00	2.88E+00
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.45E+01	1.44E+01	1.45E+01	1.45E+01
Land use	m ² a crop eq	1.01E+04	1.00E+04	1.00E+04	1.00E+04
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	7.93E+01	4.33E+01	4.33E+01	4.33E+01
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	1.88E+02	1.41E+02	1.46E+02	1.42E+02
Water consumption	m ³	7.85E+01	7.64E+01	7.66E+01	7.65E+01

Table 32: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 1 of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit.

Impact Category	Units	CS1-Y3-T1	CS1-Y3-T2	CS1-Y3-T3	CS1-Y3-T4
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	1.11E+00	8.36E-01	7.43E-01	7.09E-01
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	1.29E-05	7.58E-06	6.69E-06	6.30E-06
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	8.71E-03	5.57E-03	4.97E-03	4.64E-03
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	3.48E-04	3.29E-04	2.91E-04	2.74E-04
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	5.53E-03	5.27E-03	4.64E-03	4.38E-03
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2.00E+00	1.33E+00	1.29E+00	1.13E+00
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.31E-03	1.17E-03	1.05E-03	9.77E-04
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.82E-03	1.28E-03	1.19E-03	1.08E-03
Land use	m ² a crop eq	2.89E+00	2.82E+00	2.48E+00	2.34E+00
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	5.68E-03	4.78E-03	4.29E-03	3.98E-03

Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	2.65E-01	2.10E-01	1.90E-01	1.75E-01
Water consumption	m ³	1.90E-01	1.82E-01	1.61E-01	1.51E-01

Table 33: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 1 of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha.

Impact Category	Units	CS1-Y3-T1	CS1-Y3-T2	CS1-Y3-T3	CS1-Y3-T4
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	4.01E+03	3.09E+03	3.12E+03	3.16E+03
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	4.65E-02	2.80E-02	2.81E-02	2.80E-02
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	3.15E+01	2.06E+01	2.08E+01	2.06E+01
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	1.26E+00	1.22E+00	1.22E+00	1.22E+00
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	2.00E+01	1.95E+01	1.95E+01	1.95E+01
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	7.22E+03	4.93E+03	5.40E+03	5.03E+03
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	4.75E+00	4.33E+00	4.40E+00	4.35E+00
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	6.57E+00	4.73E+00	5.01E+00	4.79E+00
Land use	m ² a crop eq	1.04E+04	1.04E+04	1.04E+04	1.04E+04
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	2.05E+01	1.77E+01	1.80E+01	1.77E+01
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	9.56E+02	7.76E+02	7.95E+02	7.80E+02
Water consumption	m ³	6.84E+02	6.74E+02	6.74E+02	6.74E+02

Table 34: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 4 of the first year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit.

Impact Category	Units	CS4-Y1-T1	CS4-Y1-T2	CS4-Y1-T3	CS4-Y1-T4	CS4-Y1-T5
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	5.45E-01	6.93E-01	4.33E-01	4.47E-01	3.96E-01
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	7.60E-06	9.69E-06	6.28E-06	6.18E-06	5.71E-06
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	6.21E-03	7.74E-03	4.88E-03	4.95E-03	4.46E-03
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	1.39E-04	1.63E-04	9.69E-05	1.04E-04	8.82E-05
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	3.09E-03	3.95E-03	2.56E-03	2.51E-03	2.32E-03
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.27E+00	1.41E+00	7.77E-01	9.37E-01	7.41E-01
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	6.45E-03	8.11E-03	5.16E-03	5.17E-03	4.70E-03
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	6.76E-03	8.35E-03	5.21E-03	5.35E-03	4.77E-03
Land use	m ² a crop eq	1.41E+00	1.81E+00	1.17E+00	1.15E+00	1.06E+00
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	3.92E-03	4.28E-03	2.30E-03	2.88E-03	2.23E-03
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	9.73E-02	1.20E-01	7.53E-02	7.90E-02	7.07E-02
Water consumption	m ³	2.04E-02	2.56E-02	1.62E-02	1.64E-02	1.49E-02

Table 35: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 4 of the first year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha.

Impact Category	Units	CS4-Y1-T1	CS4-Y1-T2	CS4-Y1-T3	CS4-Y1-T4	CS4-Y1-T5
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Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	4.12E+03	4.11E+03	3.96E+03	4.16E+03	3.99E+03
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	5.75E-02	5.74E-02	5.75E-02	5.76E-02	5.76E-02
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	4.70E+01	4.58E+01	4.47E+01	4.62E+01	4.50E+01
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	1.05E+00	9.68E-01	8.87E-01	9.71E-01	8.90E-01
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	2.34E+01	2.34E+01	2.34E+01	2.34E+01	2.34E+01
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	9.64E+03	8.38E+03	7.11E+03	8.74E+03	7.47E+03
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	4.88E+01	4.80E+01	4.73E+01	4.82E+01	4.74E+01
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	5.12E+01	4.94E+01	4.77E+01	4.98E+01	4.81E+01
Land use	m ² a crop eq	1.07E+04	1.07E+04	1.07E+04	1.07E+04	1.07E+04
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	2.96E+01	2.54E+01	2.11E+01	2.68E+01	2.25E+01
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	7.36E+02	7.13E+02	6.89E+02	7.36E+02	7.13E+02
Water consumption	m ³	1.54E+02	1.52E+02	1.49E+02	1.53E+02	1.50E+02

Table 36: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 4 of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit.

Impact Category	Units	CS4-Y3-T1	CS4-Y3-T2	CS4-Y3-T3	CS4-Y3-T4	CS4-Y3-T5
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	2,63E-01	3,27E-01	2,75E-01	3,98E-01	2,92E-01
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	3,98E-06	5,17E-06	4,17E-06	5,75E-06	4,36E-06
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	2,95E-03	3,78E-03	3,05E-03	4,26E-03	3,21E-03
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	6,12E-05	7,70E-05	6,05E-05	8,60E-05	6,33E-05
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	1,64E-03	2,13E-03	1,73E-03	2,37E-03	1,80E-03
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	5,06E-01	6,25E-01	4,76E-01	7,30E-01	5,24E-01
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1,27E-03	1,62E-03	1,30E-03	1,82E-03	1,37E-03
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2,37E-03	3,02E-03	2,41E-03	3,40E-03	2,54E-03
Land use	m ² a crop eq	7,24E-01	9,39E-01	7,61E-01	1,04E+00	7,95E-01
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	1,46E-03	1,78E-03	1,35E-03	2,12E-03	1,51E-03
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	4,26E-02	5,47E-02	4,39E-02	6,36E-02	4,77E-02
Water consumption	m ³	1,32E-02	1,71E-02	1,38E-02	1,91E-02	1,44E-02

Table 37: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 4 of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha.

Impact Category	Units	CS4-Y3-T1	CS4-Y3-T2	CS4-Y3-T3	CS4-Y3-T4	CS4-Y3-T5
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	3.81E+03	3.65E+03	3.80E+03	4.00E+03	3.86E+03
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	5.77E-02	5.78E-02	5.76E-02	5.78E-02	5.78E-02
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	4.28E+01	4.23E+01	4.21E+01	4.29E+01	4.25E+01
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	8.88E-01	8.62E-01	8.35E-01	8.65E-01	8.38E-01

Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	2.38E+01	2.38E+01	2.38E+01	2.38E+01	2.38E+01
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	7.35E+03	6.99E+03	6.57E+03	7.34E+03	6.94E+03
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.84E+01	1.82E+01	1.80E+01	1.83E+01	1.81E+01
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	3.43E+01	3.38E+01	3.33E+01	3.42E+01	3.37E+01
Land use	m ² a crop eq	1.05E+04	1.05E+04	1.05E+04	1.05E+04	1.05E+04
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	2.12E+01	1.99E+01	1.86E+01	2.14E+01	2.00E+01
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	6.18E+02	6.12E+02	6.06E+02	6.39E+02	6.32E+02
Water consumption	m ³	1.92E+02	1.91E+02	1.90E+02	1.92E+02	1.91E+02

Table 38: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 8 of the first year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit.

Impact Category	Units	CS8-Y1-T1	CS8-Y1-T2	CS8-Y1-T3	CS8-Y1-T4
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	2.64E-01	3.17E-01	1.64E+00	3.70E-01
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	3.20E-06	4.50E-06	1.54E-05	9.66E-06
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	1.55E-03	1.60E-03	9.17E-03	5.63E-03
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	2.61E-05	1.90E-05	1.39E-05	7.36E-06
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	1.44E-03	1.45E-03	1.47E-03	1.14E-03
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.42E-01	1.46E-01	8.68E-02	5.55E-02
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	6.42E-04	6.57E-04	1.61E-04	1.42E-04
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	6.54E-04	6.62E-04	3.38E-04	2.92E-04
Land use	m ² a crop eq	4.82E-01	5.94E-01	2.57E-01	2.31E-01
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	8.69E-03	9.25E-03	1.61E-03	1.44E-03
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	3.64E-02	4.41E-02	1.74E-02	1.51E-02
Water consumption	m ³	1.97E-02	2.00E-02	1.03E-02	9.47E-03

Table 39: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 8 of the first year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha.

Impact Category	Units	CS8-Y1-T1	CS8-Y1-T2	CS8-Y1-T3	CS8-Y1-T4
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	6.05E+03	7.18E+03	7.01E+04	1.77E+04
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	7.34E-02	1.02E-01	6.62E-01	4.61E-01
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	3.55E+01	3.61E+01	3.93E+02	2.69E+02
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	5.98E-01	4.29E-01	5.96E-01	3.51E-01
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	3.31E+01	3.29E+01	6.28E+01	5.43E+01
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	3.25E+03	3.30E+03	3.72E+03	2.65E+03
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.47E+01	1.49E+01	6.88E+00	6.78E+00
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.50E+01	1.50E+01	1.45E+01	1.39E+01
Land use	m ² a crop eq	1.11E+04	1.34E+04	1.10E+04	1.10E+04
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	1.99E+02	2.09E+02	6.89E+01	6.87E+01
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	8.34E+02	9.98E+02	7.44E+02	7.19E+02
Water consumption	m ³	4.51E+02	4.53E+02	4.43E+02	4.52E+02

Table 40: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 8 of the second year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit.

Impact Category	Units	CS8-Y2-T1	CS8-Y2-T2	CS8-Y2-T3	CS8-Y2-T4
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	7.54E-01	2.15E+01	1.52E+00	7.91E-01
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	6.41E-06	1.59E-04	6.40E-06	3.35E-06
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	3.30E-03	8.62E-02	5.96E-03	3.12E-03
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	1.81E-04	2.25E-03	3.54E-04	4.28E-05
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	4.97E-03	1.01E-01	7.97E-03	4.17E-03
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	9.89E-01	2.17E+01	2.02E+00	1.05E+00
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	5.57E-03	1.07E-01	3.66E-03	1.92E-03
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.92E-03	3.93E-02	3.07E-03	1.61E-03
Land use	m ² a crop eq	2.02E+00	5.99E+01	5.43E+00	2.84E+00
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	2.28E-03	1.35E-01	1.17E-02	6.11E-03
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	1.64E-01	5.04E+00	3.89E-01	2.03E-01
Water consumption	m ³	7.76E-03	2.04E-01	1.49E-02	7.80E-03

Table 41: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 8 of the second year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha.

Impact Category	Units	CS8-Y2-T1	CS8-Y2-T2	CS8-Y2-T3	CS8-Y2-T4
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	3.87E+03	5.91E+03	4.64E+03	4.60E+03
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	3.29E-02	4.38E-02	1.95E-02	1.95E-02
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	1.69E+01	2.37E+01	1.81E+01	1.81E+01
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	9.28E-01	6.18E-01	1.08E+00	2.49E-01
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	2.55E+01	2.78E+01	2.43E+01	2.43E+01
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	5.08E+03	5.97E+03	6.14E+03	6.13E+03
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2.86E+01	2.94E+01	1.12E+01	1.11E+01
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	9.86E+00	1.08E+01	9.35E+00	9.34E+00
Land use	m ² a crop eq	1.04E+04	1.65E+04	1.65E+04	1.65E+04
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	1.17E+01	3.72E+01	3.55E+01	3.55E+01
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	8.43E+02	1.39E+03	1.18E+03	1.18E+03
Water consumption	m ³	3.99E+01	5.60E+01	4.54E+01	4.54E+01

Table 42: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 8 of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit.

Impact Category	Units	CS8-Y3-T1	CS8-Y3-T2	CS8-Y3-T3	CS8-Y3-T4
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	3.74E-01	4.67E-01	1.05E+00	9.69E-02
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	7.32E-06	7.26E-06	3.05E-05	6.49E-07
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	9.43E-03	9.33E-03	1.88E-02	5.65E-04
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	7.00E-05	4.95E-05	2.78E-05	1.11E-05

Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	3.28E-03	3.29E-03	2.45E-03	6.81E-04
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2.27E-01	2.57E-01	1.06E-01	7.24E-02
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.06E-03	1.17E-03	3.12E-04	2.13E-04
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	3.18E-04	3.44E-04	1.59E-04	1.08E-04
Land use	m ² a crop eq	7.78E-01	1.19E+00	3.37E-01	3.20E-01
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	1.29E-03	2.94E-03	3.87E-04	6.97E-04
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	7.16E-02	1.06E-01	2.32E-02	2.41E-02
Water consumption	m ³	2.65E-02	2.79E-02	9.06E-03	6.15E-03

Table 43: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 8 of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha.

Impact Category	Units	CS8-Y3-T1	CS8-Y3-T2	CS8-Y3-T3	CS8-Y3-T4
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	2.90E+03	3.49E+03	2.16E+04	2.66E+03
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	5.67E-02	5.43E-02	6.24E-01	1.78E-02
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	7.31E+01	6.98E+01	3.84E+02	1.55E+01
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	5.43E-01	3.70E-01	5.70E-01	3.05E-01
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	2.54E+01	2.46E+01	5.02E+01	1.87E+01
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.76E+03	1.92E+03	2.17E+03	1.99E+03
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	8.18E+00	8.72E+00	6.39E+00	5.84E+00
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2.47E+00	2.57E+00	3.25E+00	2.96E+00
Land use	m ² a crop eq	6.03E+03	8.87E+03	6.90E+03	8.79E+03
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	9.97E+00	2.20E+01	7.93E+00	1.91E+01
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	5.55E+02	7.93E+02	4.75E+02	6.62E+02
Water consumption	m ³	2.06E+02	2.09E+02	1.86E+02	1.69E+02

Table 44: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 9 of the second year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit.

Impact Category	Units	CS9-Y2-T1	CS9-Y2-T2	CS9-Y2-T3	CS9-Y2-T4
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	1.94E+01	2.38E+02	3.65E+02	3.69E+00
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	5.60E-04	1.82E-03	2.07E-03	2.98E-05
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	3.43E-01	1.72E+00	1.73E+00	1.98E-02
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	5.73E-04	5.89E-02	6.92E-02	9.62E-04
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	4.55E-02	2.11E+00	2.15E+00	3.45E-02
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.41E+00	1.54E+02	1.82E+02	2.24E+00
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.20E-03	1.33E-01	1.76E-01	2.06E-03
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.54E-03	1.76E-01	2.39E-01	2.53E-03
Land use	m ² a crop eq	1.82E+01	1.95E+03	2.34E+03	3.19E+01
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	1.56E-02	1.68E+00	3.23E+00	2.71E-02
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	2.84E-01	3.25E+01	7.24E+01	4.90E-01
Water consumption	m ³	1.48E-01	1.59E+01	1.70E+01	2.60E-01

Table 45: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 9 of the second year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha.

Impact Category	Units	CS9-Y2-T1	CS9-Y2-T2	CS9-Y2-T3	CS9-Y2-T4
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	9.49E+03	1.08E+03	1.63E+03	1.02E+03
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	2.74E-01	8.28E-03	9.24E-03	8.27E-03
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	1.67E+02	7.80E+00	7.73E+00	5.49E+00
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	2.80E-01	2.68E-01	3.09E-01	2.67E-01
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	2.22E+01	9.58E+00	9.59E+00	9.58E+00
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	6.87E+02	7.00E+02	8.14E+02	6.23E+02
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	5.87E-01	6.02E-01	7.86E-01	5.72E-01
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	7.52E-01	8.01E-01	1.07E+00	7.01E-01
Land use	m ² a crop eq	8.87E+03	8.87E+03	1.04E+04	8.87E+03
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	7.62E+00	7.63E+00	1.44E+01	7.51E+00
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	1.39E+02	1.48E+02	3.23E+02	1.36E+02
Water consumption	m ³	7.22E+01	7.23E+01	7.59E+01	7.22E+01

Table 46: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 9 of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit.

Impact Category	Units	CS9-Y3-T1	CS9-Y3-T2	CS9-Y3-T3	CS9-Y3-T4
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	2.51E-01	3.72E-02	5.70E-02	3.84E-02
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	6.85E-06	1.78E-07	2.05E-07	1.93E-07
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	4.24E-03	1.97E-04	2.62E-04	1.87E-04
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	4.81E-06	4.13E-06	5.13E-06	4.49E-06
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	6.43E-04	2.99E-04	3.09E-04	3.26E-04
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	5.92E-02	5.49E-02	6.21E-02	5.72E-02
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.08E-04	1.00E-04	1.11E-04	1.08E-04
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2.22E-04	2.06E-04	2.30E-04	2.20E-04
Land use	m ² a crop eq	2.42E-01	2.22E-01	2.60E-01	2.41E-01
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	2.46E-04	2.27E-04	3.74E-04	2.43E-04
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	6.05E-03	5.98E-03	1.18E-02	5.94E-03
Water consumption	m ³	9.27E-05	8.60E-05	1.66E-04	9.16E-05

Table 47: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 9 of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha.

Impact Category	Units	CS9-Y3-T1	CS9-Y3-T2	CS9-Y3-T3	CS9-Y3-T4
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	1.06E+04	1.71E+03	2.54E+03	1.62E+03
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	2.89E-01	8.17E-03	9.16E-03	8.14E-03
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	1.79E+02	9.07E+00	1.17E+01	7.89E+00
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	2.03E-01	1.90E-01	2.29E-01	1.90E-01
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	2.71E+01	1.38E+01	1.38E+01	1.38E+01

Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2.50E+03	2.53E+03	2.77E+03	2.41E+03
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	4.58E+00	4.61E+00	4.95E+00	4.56E+00
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	9.38E+00	9.49E+00	1.03E+01	9.31E+00
Land use	m ² a crop eq	1.02E+04	1.02E+04	1.16E+04	1.02E+04
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	1.04E+01	1.04E+01	1.67E+01	1.03E+01
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	2.55E+02	2.75E+02	5.29E+02	2.51E+02
Water consumption	m ³	3.91E+00	3.95E+00	7.42E+00	3.87E+00

Table 48: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 11 of the first year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha.

Impact Category	Units	CS11-Y1-T1	CS11-Y1-T2	CS11-Y1-T3
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	2.36E+03	2.22E+03	2.26E+03
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	3.20E-02	3.17E-02	3.19E-02
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	6.85E+00	6.28E+00	6.46E+00
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	9.15E+00	7.89E+00	8.58E+00
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	7.70E+00	7.18E+00	7.35E+00
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	9.36E+00	8.07E+00	8.78E+00
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	3.86E+01	3.74E+01	3.77E+01
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.29E+00	1.24E+00	1.25E+00
Land use	m ² a crop eq	9.53E+00	9.51E+00	9.81E+00
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	1.31E+04	1.24E+04	1.27E+04
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	2.82E+01	1.63E+01	1.65E+01
Water consumption	m ³	1.49E+01	9.85E+00	1.02E+01

Table 49: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 11 of the second year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha.

Impact Category	Units	CS11-Y2-T1	CS11-Y2-T2	CS11-Y2-T3
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	3.24E+03	3.22E+03	3.27E+03
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	3.38E-02	3.38E-02	3.38E-02
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	8.34E+00	8.34E+00	8.34E+00
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	1.22E+01	1.22E+01	1.22E+01
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	7.78E+00	7.78E+00	7.78E+00
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.25E+01	1.25E+01	1.25E+01
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.68E+01	1.68E+01	1.68E+01
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2.65E+00	2.65E+00	2.65E+00
Land use	m ² a crop eq	1.03E+01	1.03E+01	1.03E+01
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	2.50E+03	2.50E+03	2.50E+03
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	2.46E+00	2.46E+00	2.46E+00
Water consumption	m ³	2.38E+00	2.38E+00	2.38E+00

Table 50: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 11 of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha.

Impact Category	Units	CS11-Y3-T1	CS11-Y3-T2	CS11-Y3-T3
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	2.41E+03	2.39E+03	2.40E+03
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	2.07E-02	2.07E-02	2.07E-02
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	6.05E+00	6.05E+00	6.05E+00
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	1.22E+01	1.22E+01	1.22E+01
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	6.41E+00	6.41E+00	6.41E+00
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.23E+01	1.23E+01	1.23E+01
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2.61E+01	2.61E+01	2.61E+01
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.29E+00	1.29E+00	1.29E+00
Land use	m ² a crop eq	8.83E+00	8.83E+00	8.83E+00
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	7.32E+03	7.32E+03	7.32E+03
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	2.25E+02	2.25E+02	2.25E+02
Water consumption	m ³	2.66E+01	2.66E+01	2.66E+01

Table 51: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 14b of the first year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit.

Impact Category	Units	CS14b-Y1-T1	CS14b-Y1-T2
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	2.77E-01	4.71E-01
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	2.87E-06	3.69E-06
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	3.12E-03	3.93E-03
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	6.16E-04	4.09E-04
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	1.45E-03	1.87E-03
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	5.73E-01	7.31E-01
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	3.47E-04	4.38E-04
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	5.42E-04	6.69E-04
Land use	m ² a crop eq	7.19E+00	9.26E+00
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	5.13E-03	6.61E-03
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	8.24E-02	1.01E-01
Water consumption	m ³	3.88E-02	5.00E-02

Table 52: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 14b of the first year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha.

Impact Category	Units	CS14b-Y1-T1	CS14b-Y1-T2
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	3.30E+02	4.35E+02
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	3.42E-03	3.41E-03
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	3.71E+00	3.64E+00
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	7.34E-01	3.78E-01
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	1.73E+00	1.73E+00

Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	6.83E+02	6.75E+02
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	4.13E-01	4.05E-01
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	6.45E-01	6.18E-01
Land use	m ² a crop eq	8.56E+03	8.56E+03
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	6.12E+00	6.11E+00
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	9.81E+01	9.32E+01
Water consumption	m ³	4.63E+01	4.63E+01

Table 53: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 14b of the second year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit.

Impact Category	Units	CS14b-Y2-T1	CS14b-Y2-T2
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	2.23E-01	2.51E-01
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	2.19E-06	2.37E-06
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	1.68E-03	1.83E-03
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	5.54E-04	2.78E-04
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	1.88E-03	2.04E-03
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	6.94E-01	7.53E-01
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.72E-03	1.86E-03
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	3.98E-03	4.32E-03
Land use	m ² a crop eq	7.32E+00	7.94E+00
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	4.48E-04	4.86E-04
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	2.57E-02	2.80E-02
Water consumption	m ³	2.14E-02	2.32E-02

Table 54: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 14b of the second year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha.

Impact Category	Units	CS14b-Y2-T1	CS14b-Y2-T2
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	3.39E+02	3.51E+02
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	3.32E-03	3.32E-03
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	2.55E+00	2.56E+00
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	8.41E-01	3.89E-01
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	2.86E+00	2.86E+00
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.05E+03	1.05E+03
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2.61E+00	2.61E+00
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	6.04E+00	6.04E+00
Land use	m ² a crop eq	1.11E+04	1.11E+04
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	6.81E-01	6.81E-01
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	3.90E+01	3.92E+01
Water consumption	m ³	3.25E+01	3.25E+01

Table 55: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 14b of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1€ of profit.

Impact Category	Units	CS14b-Y3-T1	CS14b-Y3-T2
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	1.07E+00	6.44E-01
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	5.06E-06	3.69E-06
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	4.24E-03	3.02E-03
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	9.11E-04	3.44E-04
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	2.42E-03	1.77E-03
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2.41E-01	1.70E-01
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	5.29E-04	3.79E-04
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	4.75E-04	3.25E-04
Land use	m ² a crop eq	1.09E+01	7.91E+00
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	1.47E-03	1.07E-03
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	6.10E-02	4.02E-02
Water consumption	m ³	6.65E-02	4.85E-02

Table 56: Environmental characterization of case study (CS) 14b of the third year (Y) of the crop rotation, for each of the different treatments (T). Functional unit: 1 ha.

Impact Category	Units	CS14b-Y3-T1	CS14b-Y3-T2
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	8.66E+02	7.16E+02
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	4.11E-03	4.10E-03
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	3.44E+00	3.36E+00
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	7.39E-01	3.83E-01
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	1.97E+00	1.96E+00
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.95E+02	1.89E+02
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	4.29E-01	4.21E-01
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	3.86E-01	3.62E-01
Land use	m ² a crop eq	8.81E+03	8.81E+03
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	1.19E+00	1.19E+00
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	4.95E+01	4.47E+01
Water consumption	m ³	5.39E+01	5.39E+01

8. Annex C: Impact contribution per factors

Figure 62: Impact contribution per factor for case study 4 of the first year of the crop rotation. Global warming (GW), Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), Terrestrial acidification (TA), Freshwater eutrophication (FET), Marine eutrophication (MET), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), Marine ecotoxicity (MEC), Land use (LU), Mineral resource scarcity (MR), Fossil resource scarcity (FR), and Water use (WU).

